

Effect of vitamin C deprivation on the duration of colds in the Sheffield study (1953): a statistical analysis

Harri Hemilä, MD, PhD

Department of Public Health, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, FINLAND.

harri.hemila@helsinki.fi

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4710-307X>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/?term=hemila+h+vitamin>

<https://researchportal.helsinki.fi/fi/persons/harri-hemil%C3%A4>

<https://scholar.google.fi/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

Location of this file:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14717360>

version 2. 2025-12-30 (minor revisions)

Summary

The Sheffield study on the vitamin C requirement of adult humans was carried out in the UK from 1944 to 1946. The main goal was to establish the minimum effective dose of vitamin C needed to cure scurvy. The participants were 19 men and 1 woman, aged 21-34; they lived a normal life without strenuous physical work. However, the findings are inherently limited, given the predominantly male sample, the small age range, and the generally sedentary lifestyles of participants.

Although the Sheffield study is small and old, it is a study of great importance. Notably it is the first reference in the current UK recommendations for vitamin C. For ethical reasons it is highly unlikely that a similar trial will be carried out in the future. Therefore, a critical analysis of the data in the Sheffield study remains relevant. A recent (2022) reanalysis of the study showed that the original conclusions regarding the impact of vitamin C on scar strength were flawed.

In the Sheffield study, participants were divided into 3 groups: 10 participants were “deprived” and not given vitamin C supplements (their diets contained ~1 mg/day), 7 participants were administered 10 mg/day vitamin C as a supplement, and 3 participants were administered 70 mg/day.

One of the recorded outcomes was the duration of common cold episodes. The statistician for the study (C. H. Jowett) calculated that colds lasted on average 6.4 days during vitamin C deprivation, compared with 3.3 days on the 10-70 mg/day dosage. Thus, deprivation nearly doubled the duration of colds. Jowett concluded that “*such evidence as there is, however, definitely confirms the hypothesis that the absence of vitamin C tended to cause colds to last longer*” and “*the data support the hypothesis that colds of deprived subjects lasted longer, but do not establish it.*”

In this paper, the data on common cold duration is reanalyzed. A total of 18 cold episodes occurred during vitamin C deprivation, while 21 cold episodes were recorded when participants received 10-70 mg/day vitamin C.

Vitamin C deprivation increased the duration of colds on average by 77% (P = 0.014).

Vitamin C deprivation decreased the cold recovery rate by 60% (P = 0.008).

Vitamin C deprivation extended the duration of 1-day colds by 2.2 days (95% CI 1.0 to 5.4 days).

The finding that vitamin C deprivation prolonged the duration of colds was not reported in the trial summaries published in the Lancet (1948) or the Proceedings of the Nutrition Society (1953). Moreover, this effect on cold duration is absent from the current UK recommendations for vitamin C. As a consequence, the findings related to the common cold from the Sheffield trial have been largely overlooked and underreported for decades.

Contents	Page
Background	3
Observations on the common cold	4
References to the Sheffield study	6
Reanalysis of the data on common cold duration in the Sheffield study	
A. Data and the repeat of the Jowett (1953) analysis	7
B. Difference in the proportion of short 1-day colds	8
C. Relative effect of vitamin C deprivation on common cold duration	10
D. Recovery rate from the common cold using Cox-regression	11
E. Quantile treatment effect (QTE) of vitamin C deprivation	12
Discussion	
Ethical issues with intentionally causing scurvy in experimental subjects	14
Vitamin C and respiratory infection research before 1948	17
The common colds of vitamin C deprived subjects lasted longer	19
Flawed conclusions about causal effects	20
The Sheffield study has had great influence on the vitamin C recommendation in the UK	21
Bias against vitamin C for infections	22
Conclusions	22
Other references	23
Appendix	
1. Summary of the Sheffield study	31
2. Common colds in the Sheffield study	33
3. Data set based on Appendix 2	39
4. Findings in the Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) trial	40
5. Statistical issues	45
6. Replication of the Jowett (1953) analysis	47
7. Relative effect	49
8. Cox regression	50
9. QTE analysis	51
10. Vitamin C deficiency and pneumonia in Alfred Hess' monograph on scurvy (1920)	53
11. Findings in the Cowan et al. (1942) trial	58
12. Benefit from vitamin C for common colds in UK trials after the Sheffield study	60
13. Possible socio-political roots for the bias against vitamin C supplements	61

Background

The Sheffield study on the vitamin C requirement for human adults was carried out at the Sorby Research Institute at Sheffield, England, under the supervision of Hans Krebs (1953 Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine) from October 1944 to February 1946 [1-16]. A summary of the study was published in the *Lancet* in 1948 [4]. In 1953, another summary by Hans Krebs was published [5], along with the detailed 179-page final report [6-9].

The selection of participants and the methods were summarized by Krebs as follows [5]:

The main plan was to induce scurvy by a vitamin C-deficient diet and to establish the minimum dose of the vitamin that cures scurvy. A subsidiary aim was to study the clinical signs and symptoms of scurvy and to correlate them with laboratory findings (p.238).

Nineteen men and one woman, aged 21-34, volunteered for the experiment. They lived a normal life without strenuous physical work. Their basal diet was designed to be as low as possible in vitamin C but complete in every other respect. It was sufficiently varied to be acceptable. From chemical analyses it was calculated that on the average a volunteer obtained not more than 1 mg vitamin C daily from the diet (p.238).

The majority were conscientious objectors [pacifists] who had convictions which did not allow them to carry arms, but who did not wish to eschew hardship and danger. They offered themselves to serve a cause they considered good. They were fully aware of the nature of the trial and of the risks it involved (p.246).

To obtain base-line data the trial began with a preliminary period, in most cases of 6 weeks, on a complete diet including about 70 mg vitamin C daily. At the end of the period all the volunteers were given the basal deficient diet and divided into three groups, ten having no supplements, seven 10 mg of vitamin C daily, and three 70 mg vitamin C daily. The group receiving 70 mg was intended to serve as a positive control and the group receiving 10 mg as a prophylactic test (p.238).

The volunteers did not know to which group they belonged, nor did the physicians responsible for the clinical investigation. All the volunteers were daily given seven supplementary tablets of identical taste and appearance, some containing vitamin C, the others being dummies. Investigations, made on the volunteers at regular intervals, included general clinical examinations, chemical analyses of blood and urine, haematological examinations, capillary-fragility tests, capillaroscopy, radiography, electrocardiography, studies of fatigue, and studies of experimental wounds (p.238).

Important clinically relevant data were collected and reported. For example, 2 of the 10 participants with vitamin C deprivation (Milburn [6,8; p.80-81] and "Another" [6,8; p.87]) suffered from acute cardiac events, which were relieved with immediate large doses of vitamin C [4-6,8]. A third deprived person (Williams, D) had pain in chest and shortness of breath after half a year of vitamin C deficiency. X-ray of chest revealed paravertebral abscess and an erosion of the 8th dorsal vertebra, which was interpreted as an active tuberculosis lesion. The condition was relieved with 500 mg/day vitamin C for 10 days. The study authors concluded that "*although the process probably began before the deficient diet started it is likely that its development was precipitated by the [vitamin C] deprivation*" [6,8; p.84-85]. A fourth deprived man (Drake) developed effusions into left knee joint after a long walk after half a year of vitamin C deprivation [6,8; p.78]. Swelling of the knee reduced after dosing 10 mg/day vitamin C.

Observations on the common cold

Throughout the Sheffield study the volunteers recorded *the number and duration of the colds* they experienced. The collected data are published in Table 44 of the main report [6, pp.134-135], with the discussion of the findings [6, pp.43-44]; see **Appendix 1-3**. The study authors described their impression of the results in the trial report as follows [6, p.43]:

At a glance [the data] seemed to indicate that the average number of colds in the deprived and non-deprived groups did not differ markedly, but that they lasted longer in the deprived group. The material was accordingly submitted to a statistician (C. H. Jowett) for analysis, who summarized his investigation as follows...

The statistician C. H. Jowett wrote in the final report (p.43-44):

The lengths of all colds were subjected to the transformation $y = 20 \log x$. It was considered that this would make the various distributions on which the statistical tests depended more close to 'normal'. The data analysed consisted of the following:

Colds of members of deprived group before dosing.
Colds of members of supplemented group up to and including July 1945.

...

Such evidence as there is, however, definitely confirms the hypothesis that the absence of vitamin C tended to cause colds to last longer.

The geometric mean length of colds of non-deprived subjects = 3.3 days
The geometric mean length of colds of deprived subjects = 6.4 days

...

Conclusion

The data support the hypothesis that colds of deprived subjects lasted longer, but do not establish it.

The Lancet report [4] and the 1953 short report [5] did not mention the doubling of common cold duration in the deprived subjects. They mentioned only the negative findings on common cold incidence. The former stated that in volunteers deprived of vitamin C there was "*no increased incidence of infection*" [4, p.854]. In the latter, Krebs wrote that "*Negative findings during the period of deprivation included ... no increased incidence of infection*" [5, p.240].

It is evident that the comparison of 10 vitamin C deprived volunteers with 10 volunteers receiving vitamin C does not have the statistical power to test modest size effects on the incidence of colds. In comparison, Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) compared 335 boys in a boarding school (~200 mg/day vitamin C) with 1100 control boys (10-15 mg/day vitamin C from foods) and found a 17% lower incidence of colds ($P = 0.047$) and a 100% decrease in the incidence of pneumonia ($P = 0.005$); see **Appendix 4 and 5**. Obviously, with the 33- to 110-fold smaller size of the Sheffield study, it is uninformative about the possible effects of vitamin C deprivation on the incidence of the common cold or pneumonia. It is a matter of opinion whether a potential 17% decrease in common cold incidence is large enough to be of practical interest. However, such an effect may also indicate broader physiological effects of vitamin C, such as influence on pneumonia, which is a much more rare event, and on days spent in the sick room due to various infections; see Appendix 4.

In the summary, the final report stated [6]:

8. In the deprived group there was no change in body weight and no increased incidence of infection although colds seemed to last longer.

See Appendix 1 for more detail.

Neither of the short summaries [4,5] nor the final report noted that there were so few participants in the Sheffield study that it was uninformative about the incidence of colds yet both of them made firm negative statements. Furthermore, neither of the short summaries mentioned that colds were twice as long in the vitamin C deprived participants even though in the text section the long report states “*The data support the hypothesis that colds of deprived subjects lasted longer*” [6, p.44]. When the observation indicates that vitamin C deprivation may double the duration of colds, it would seem relevant to encourage further research to corroborate the finding, and to investigate dose dependency and potential variation in effects between different life-style contexts. Unfortunately, such encouragement was not expressed in the short reports [4,5], and not even in the summary of the concise account of the long report [6,7; pp.6-21,143-4]; see Appendix 1.

This report reanalyzes the duration of common colds in the Sheffield study.

References to the Sheffield study

1. Sorby Research Institute. *Wikipedia*. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sorby_Research_Institute also: https://archives.shef.ac.uk/agents/corporate_entities/143 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kenneth_Mellanby
2. Rasmussen, L. (eds) *Human Guinea Pigs, by Kenneth Mellanby: A Reprint with Commentaries*. Philosophy and Medicine, vol. 134; Springer, Cham. [Describes the context for the trial]. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-37697-0>
3. Krebs H, Martin A. The War Years (1939-1945). In: *Reminiscences and Reflections*. 1981; pp. 119–125. Zenodo 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14866790>
4. Vitamin C requirement of human adults; experimental study of vitamin-C deprivation in man. [Summary]. *Lancet*. 1948;1(6510):853-8. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(48\)90572-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(48)90572-8)
- 4a. Vitamin C. [Summary]. *BMJ* 1948;2(Nov 6):828-829. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.2.4583.828> <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2091948> <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25365390>
- 4b. Vitamin C requirements. [Summary]. *BMJ* 1954;1(Apr 3):806-807. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.1.4865.806> <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2084857>
5. Krebs H. The Sheffield experiment on the vitamin C requirement of human adults. [Summary]. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*. 1953;12(3):237-46. <https://doi.org/10.1079/PNS19530054>
6. Vitamin C requirement of human adults. *Spec Rep Ser Med Res Counc (GB)*. 1953;280:1-179. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/13119061> [see the Summary in Appendix 1]
7. Introduction; Historical Account; Concise Account of the Experiment; Summary. In: Vitamin C requirement of human adults. *Spec Rep Ser Med Res Counc (GB)*. 1953;280:1-21,143-4. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14628064>
8. Introduction; Historical Account; Case Reports; References. In: Vitamin C requirement of human adults. *Spec Rep Ser Med Res Counc (GB)*. 1953;280:1-8,73-88,176-9. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7661782>
9. Diet. In: Vitamin C requirement of human adults. *Spec Rep Ser Med Res Counc (GB)*. 1953;280:56-69. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14628199>
10. Experimental scurvy. *Lancet*. 1954;263:197-8. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(54\)91268-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(54)91268-4)
11. Waife SO. Man's requirement for vitamin C. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 1954;2(4):273-4. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/2.4.273>
12. Pemberton J. The BMJ's Nuremberg issue. Nobody died during experiments on vitamin C and vitamin A intakes in Sheffield. *BMJ*. 1997;314(7078):440. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9040399>
see comments:
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/8973237/> (Weidling)
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9133906/> (Addis)
13. Pemberton J. Medical experiments carried out in Sheffield on conscientious objectors to military service during the 1939-45 war. *Int J Epidemiol*. 2006;35(3):556-8. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyl020>
14. Commentary: guinea-pigs' private war. *Int J Epidemiol*. 2006;35(3):558-60. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyl031>
15. Pemberton J. Unrecognised scurvy. Signs and requirements. *BMJ*. 2010;340:c590. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.c590>
16. Hujoel PP, Hujoel MLA. Vitamin C and scar strength: analysis of a historical trial and implications for collagen-related pathologies. [Reanalysis of the scar strength data]. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2022;115(1):8-17. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/nqab262>

Reanalysis of the data on common cold duration in the Sheffield study

A. Data and the repeat of the Jowett (1953) analysis

I repeated the analysis of variance by Jowett.

The data set in Appendix 3 collects the observations selected by Jowett [6, p.43]:

“colds of members of deprived group before dosing”

“colds of members of supplemented group up to and including July 1945”

The current analysis yields similar results to those found by Jowett, as detailed in **Appendix 6**. The minor differences may be explained by less accurate pencil and paper calculations in the late 1940s.

The same data set was used in analyses **B** to **E**.

The duration of colds has a skewed spread and the log transformation used by Jowett is insufficient to lead to a distribution approximating the normal distribution; see Appendix 6. There is a high proportion of 1-day colds when participants were administered vitamin C, and no transformation can make such a cluster approach a normal distribution. On the other hand, the 1-day colds can be analyzed as a separate binary outcome; see analysis **B**.

Assuming a uniform difference of 3.1-day longer colds (6.4 – 3.3 days calculated by Jowett, see above: “Observations on the common cold”) may be overly simplistic. For example, 2-day colds in the vitamin C deprived participants cannot be shortened by 3.1 days by taking vitamin C. The relative effect is a more informative approach; see analysis **C**.

Cox regression is useful for the analysis of duration data and does not assume a uniform difference such as a 3.1 day effect over the whole distribution; see analysis **D**.

The number of participants in the Sheffield study is so small that subgroup analyses cannot be undertaken. Nevertheless, the quantile treatment effect (QTE) analysis does not assume a uniform effect and can be more informative than assuming a uniform effect; see analysis **E**.

B. Difference in the proportion of short 1-day colds

This analysis compared the proportion of short 1-day colds between the vitamin C deprived participants and those who were administered 10-70 mg/day vitamin C. This approach does not require the assumption that the data are normally distributed. If a substantial proportion of colds are shortened to 1-day colds due to vitamin C, that is relevant even if there are no effects on the distribution of colds that are longer.

Among the 10 men administered 10-70 mg/day vitamin C, there were 21 colds. See the data set in Appendix 3. The maximum number of colds per person was 6 (Golding), and 4 participants had 3-4 colds per person. Four participants had no colds during the vitamin C periods. In this group, 7 of the 21 colds (33%) were short 1-day colds.

Among the 10 men deprived of vitamin C, there were 18 colds during the deprivation period. The maximum number of colds per person was 7 (Tridgell), and 2 participants had 3 colds per person. Four participants had no colds during the follow-up. In this group, 0 of the 18 colds (0%) were short 1-day colds.

Ignoring the fact that there were several colds per person for some participants, there was a significant difference in the proportion of 1-day colds between the participants with vitamin C deprivation and those who were administered vitamin C 10-70 mg/day with $P = 0.004$; see below. The mid-P and 1-tail were used in the calculation of the P value; see Appendix 5.

In this comparison, the Number Needed for Harm (NNH) [17,18] due to vitamin C deprivation is 3; based on $1/(33\% - 0\%)$. This means that 1 in 3 colds in the deprived group was not a short 1-day cold because of the vitamin C deprivation.

```
> riskratio.small(SheffieldJowett$Deprived, SheffieldJowett$Days_1)
$data
      Outcome
Predictor  0 1 Total
      0    14 7    21
      1    18 0    18
      Total 32 7    39

$P.value
      two-sided
Predictor midp.exact fisher.exact chi.square
      0          NA          NA          NA
      1    0.00756    0.009629    0.006848

> (P_1tail=0.00756/2)
[1] 0.00378
```

A similar calculation was undertaken using only 1 cold per person, the shortest cold for each person, which means that there is a single observation for each participant who had at least one cold. In this calculation, the units of analysis are independent.

Among the 6 participants administered 10-70 mg/day vitamin C who had colds during the follow-up, there were 4 participants whose shortest colds were just 1 day.

Among the 6 participants deprived of vitamin C who had colds, none had colds shorter than 2 days; see Appendix 3.

For the difference in the proportions of 1-day colds between the vitamin C deprived participants and those administered vitamin C, **P = 0.015**.

```
> riskratio.small(SheffieldShortest)
$data
      Outcome
Predictor Disease1 Disease2 Total
Exposed1      2         4      6
Exposed2      6         0      6
Total         8         4     12

$P.value
      two-sided
Predictor midp.exact fisher.exact chi.square
Exposed1      NA         NA         NA
Exposed2    0.0303     0.0606     0.0143

> (P_1tail=0.0303/2)
[1] 0.0152
```

C. Relative effect of vitamin C deprivation on common cold duration

As noted above, it is clear that 2-day colds in the vitamin C deprived participants cannot be shortened by 3.1 days with vitamin C which is the average treatment effect using Jowett's estimates. However, the relative scale is applicable also to short common cold durations; see Appendix 5 for a description of the relative scale.

If we use Jowett's estimates, deprivation increases cold duration on average by 94% ($6.4/3.3 = 1.94$).

The current estimation in **Appendix 7** indicates that vitamin C deprivation increased the duration of colds by 77% (95% CI: 6-195%; **P = 0.014**).

The difference between 77% and 94% is explained by Jowett's calculation of the geometric means and by possible inaccuracies in the manual calculations undertaken in the 1940s.

D. Recovery rate from the common cold using Cox-regression

Cox regression of recovery from the common cold indicates that the recovery rate was 60% (95% CI: 14-81%, **P = 0.008**) lower in the vitamin C deprived participants; see **Fig. 1** and **Appendix 8**.

Fig. 1. Survival curves of common cold recovery for participants with vitamin C deprivation and vitamin C administration (10-70 mg/day).

E. Quantile treatment effect (QTE) of vitamin C deprivation

In the quantile treatment effect (QTE) analysis, the distribution in the control group outcome is plotted on the x-axis. The difference in the outcome between the 2 groups is plotted on the y-axis [19-24]. Usually, the x-axis shows the quantiles of the outcome distribution [19,20], but back-transformation to the original scale was formulated recently [22] and is used in this analysis. The QTE largely corresponds to looking at the difference between 2 survival curves in the horizontal direction rather than the vertical direction [20]. The QTE approach is effective for analyzing whether the treatment effect varies over the outcome level.

In **Fig. 2A**, the x-axis shows the common cold duration while participants were administered 10-70 mg/day vitamin C as the control. The y-axis shows the difference between the two groups for the QTE effect. According to this estimation, 1-day colds during the periods of vitamin C administration were 2.2 days (95% CI: 1.0 to 5.4 days) longer in the deprivation period; see **Appendix 9**. The effect was greater for longer colds, but the confidence intervals are wider. The point estimates indicate that colds during the deprived period were 5 to 6 days longer, when the colds in the vitamin C administration period were 5 to 8 days long. The *bqte* program [23] used in this analysis uses bootstrapping [25], and there cannot be a null effect on the 1-day colds in the vitamin C period since there were no 1-day colds in the vitamin C deprived period; see Fig.1.

In **Fig. 2B**, the x-axis shows the common cold duration in participants with vitamin C deprivation as the control. The y-axis shows the QTE effect. In this presentation it is evident that 3-day colds in the vitamin C deprived period cannot be shortened by 4.0 days which is the average treatment effect in this calculation. According to this estimation, 3-day colds during the period of vitamin C deprivation were on average 1.68 days shorter in the vitamin C administration period; see Appendix 9.

Fig. 2. Quantile treatment effect of vitamin C on common cold duration.
 A: Using vitamin C administration (10-70 mg/day) as the control on the x-axis.
 B: Using vitamin C deprivation as the control on the x-axis.
 The plots are calculated with the *bqte* program [22-23]. The blue dotted line indicates the average treatment effect (4.0 days in this estimation). The red dots indicate the point estimate for each day. The black vertical lines indicate the 95% confidence intervals; see Appendix 9.

Discussion

Ethical issues with intentionally causing scurvy in experimental subjects

The Sheffield study is particularly important. It is probably the most important placebo-controlled study for understanding the clinical effects of vitamin C deficiency. John Pemberton was responsible for the clinical examinations that involved recording the known and suspected signs of scurvy as they appeared and the occurrence of any other illnesses [13]. As an illustration of the significance of the study, he wrote in 2006 that “*A search of the literature since 1945 revealed very few studies of human vitamin C deprivation continued to the stage of clinical scurvy and none that had so many subjects as in the Sheffield experiment or that included a control group and continued for as long*” [13].

Pemberton also considered that “*bearing in mind the strict requirements of the Declaration of Helsinki on medical research involving human subjects, it is unlikely that a similar opportunity for human experimentation under the conditions and on the scale of the Sheffield experiments will be available in the foreseeable future*” [13].

Referring to the 2 cases of acute cardiac events in the Sheffield study, Krebs wrote in 1953:

The pathological process underlying this cardiac emergency is bound to remain uncertain. The older records of scurvy contain many references to sudden death. Lind (1757, [26, p.137]) writes: ‘*Persons that appear to be but slightly scorbutic, are apt to be suddenly and unexpectedly seized with some of its worse symptoms. Their dropping down dead upon an exertion of their strength, or change of air, is not easily foretold*’. As these incidents occur at a stage when multiple skin petechiae are the main clinical manifestation of scurvy, and when general fitness still appears to be fairly good, it is not improbable that a haemorrhage at a critical point of the conducting system of the heart forms the basis of the cardiac syndrome [5, pp.239-240].

In the concluding section of the 1953 summary, Krebs wrote:

I must pay tribute to the young men and woman who volunteered to act as human ‘guinea-pigs’. The majority were conscientious objectors who had convictions which did not allow them to carry arms, but who did not wish to eschew hardship and danger. They offered themselves to serve a cause they considered good. They were fully aware of the nature of the trial and of the risks it involved. When the Committee decided on account of the cardiac incidents to shorten the period of deprivation in certain cases the volunteers let it be known as their wish that considerations for their personal safety should not stand in the way of pursuing the object of the trial. Fortunately they suffered only temporary disabilities. No permanent harm was done [5, p.246; see also ref. 3].

One may wonder what the ethical considerations were in the 1940s when the Sheffield trial was being planned. A decade earlier, the Lancet published the story of William Starr, who had self-experimented with diet in the 18th century and eventually died of scurvy [27]. That paper was not cited in the Sheffield final report [6-8].

James Lind’s treatise on scurvy is cited in the Sheffield study final report [6-8]; however, the Introduction, Historical Account and Concise Account of the Experiment sections make no mention of the sudden deaths among scurvy patients described by Lind [26,28].

In his treatise on scurvy, to which Krebs cites above, Lind (1757) [26, p.v-vi] described captain Hawking's experiences as follows:

It is now above 150 years since that great sea-officer, Sir John Hawkins, in his observations made in a voyage to the South sea, remarked it [scurvy] to be the pestilence of that element. He was able, in the course of twenty years, in which he had been employed at sea, to give an account of 10,000 mariners destroyed by it.

Lind (1757) [26, p.435] described the occurrence of scurvy also on commander George Anson's voyage as follows:

For many of our people, though confined to their hammocks, appeared to have no inconsiderable share of health; for they eat and drank heartily, were chearful, and talked with much seeming vigour, and with a loud strong tone of voice; and yet on their being the least moved, tho' it was only from one part of the ship to the other, and that in their hammocks, they have immediately expired. And others, who have confided in their seeming strength, and have resolved to get out of their hammocks, have died before they could well reach the deck. And it was no uncommon thing for those who could do some kind of duty, and walk the deck, to drop down dead in an instant, on any endeavours to act with their utmost vigour; many of our people having perished in this manner, during the course of this voyage.

In his thorough review on scurvy, George Budd (1840) wrote [29, p.83]:

We have already spoken of the debility, and the tendency to swoon, in persons affected with scurvy. In high degrees of scurvy this tendency is so great, that the slightest motion, the erect posture even, occasions fainting, which sometimes proves fatal. The fact that scorbutic persons not unfrequently expire suddenly, on any exertion of strength, has, indeed, been noticed by all writers on scurvy, as constituting one of its most remarkable features.

Considering the high mortality associated with scurvy in historical records, there should have been, and still should be, serious ethical concerns about deliberately inducing scurvy in human subjects, even in the mid-twentieth century.

Furthermore, before the Sheffield study, there were several reports in the medical literature about scurvy causing cardiac disorders [30-43], which were also discussed in many sections of Alfred Hess' monograph (1920). This monograph was the most important book on scurvy in the early 20th century, published well before the Sheffield study [28,44]. A Crimean War report (1858) also indicated that scurvy caused pathological cardiac damage [45, p.176]: "*Post-mortem Appearances... It seems, also, probable that the extreme debility of the heart... in some measure also to the weakened muscular power, and to participation in the general flaccidity and want of consistence in the tissues, which scurvy induced.*"

Given this long history of scurvy causing cardiac disorders, the 2 cardiac emergencies occurring during the Sheffield study were not unexpected. However, the previous reports of cardiac disorders with scurvy were not considered in the Sheffield final report [6-8], nor in the brief summaries [4,5].

When the final report is 179 pages long, one would expect that the researchers had carefully reviewed the literature on scurvy when planning the trial and when writing the final report. However, the report does not indicate that the researchers had done a thorough literature review on scurvy, as the potential dangers of intentionally causing vitamin C deficiency were not given due consideration.

After the 1953 report there have been many further reports indicating that vitamin C deficiency has harmful effects on cardiac function [46-61]. Deaths caused by scurvy are not just historical – there are also recent cases of scurvy deaths [62-66]. Thus, the harms of vitamin C deficiency did not end with the old descriptions of sudden deaths in the Age of Sail [26,28,29].

Pemberton wrote in 1997 [12]:

None of the volunteers died in either the vitamin C deprivation experiment or the vitamin A deprivation experiment that preceded it, although one man, Milburn, came close to death in the vitamin C experiment. After spending 229 days on a diet as deficient in vitamin C as we could make it he had clear evidence of scurvy, including bleeding gums and haemorrhages round the hair follicles of the legs. One night, after these signs had appeared, he developed all the major symptoms of coronary thrombosis. He was treated at once with intravenous vitamin C and recovered completely [dosage: “an intravenous injection of 1 g. vitamin C was given with 6 g. vitamin C by mouth at 11.20 a.m.” ref. 6,8, p.80].

While it is fortunate that Milburn survived, the circumstances described in the study appear alarmingly close to a game of Russian roulette. In his 1757 summary of earlier literature, Lind noted that many scurvy patients collapsed and died suddenly without obvious anticipatory symptoms (see above and [26,28]). Thus, it may have been sheer luck that neither of the two individuals who experienced cardiac emergencies died.

Given the extensive evidence that vitamin C deficiency can lead to acute cardiac events and death, it seems highly unlikely that in future there will be any trial comparable to the Sheffield study in which the test group is administered ≤ 1 mg/day vitamin C for half a year and longer. Given this, it is worthwhile analyzing the data collected in the Sheffield study as extensively as reasonable.

Recently Hujoel and Hujoel reanalysed the data on scar strength in the Sheffield study [16]. They showed that vitamin C intake that averaged 10 mg/day over a mean follow-up of 11.5 months was associated with a 42% weakened scar strength when compared with a vitamin C intake of 80 mg/day ($P < 0.001$). They concluded that:

the observed dose-response curve between scar strength and vitamin C intake suggests that the daily vitamin C intake needed to prevent collagen-related pathologies is in the range recommended by the National Academy of Medicine and the European Food Safety Authority (75 to 110 mg/day), not the WHO recommendation (45 mg/day).

They also concluded that “*the prior lack of statistical analyses of a landmark trial may have led to a misleading narrative on the vitamin C needs for the prevention and treatment of collagen-related pathologies*” [16]. Thus, the original statistical analysis was insufficient, and the widely repeated conclusion that the Sheffield study showed that 10 mg/day leads to maximal recovery of wounds is false.

It was timely to also reanalyze the data on common cold duration.

Vitamin C and respiratory infection research before 1948

The Sheffield study was not carried out in a vacuum, as there were several previous papers in the medical literature on vitamin C and respiratory infections. However, they were not properly discussed in the long report [6-8] and not mentioned at all in the short reports that simply stated that vitamin C did not influence the number of colds in the Sheffield trial [4,5].

Thomas Barlow (1894), who identified infantile scurvy (Barlow's disease), stated in his Bradshaw lecture that "*Eleven years ago I submitted to the consideration of members of our profession the results of an analysis of thirty-one cases of what I believed to be infantile scurvy... If the cachexia is very profound the supervention of bronchitis, pleuro-pneumonia, severe diarrhæa, or an intercurrent exanthem may bring about a fatal issue*" [67]. Thus, Barlow considered that scurvy may be associated with an elevated risk of severe respiratory infections.

Alfred Hess was an American pediatrician who appears the most important clinical researcher on scurvy in the 20th century. In his monograph (1920) [28,44] and papers [68-70], Hess described that vitamin C deficiency increases the risk of pneumonia and other infections in guinea pigs and humans; see **Appendix 10**.

Albert Sabin reported on his studies with rhesus monkeys that "*... it was found that monkeys on a scorbutic diet died of spontaneous acute infections, chiefly pneumonia and enterocolitis, while their mates receiving an adequate diet remained well*" [71].

Although findings in guinea pigs and rhesus monkeys do not directly translate to effects in humans, they should have provoked a deeper consideration of the role of vitamin C in human infections. In addition, Hess also treated children and not just guinea pigs.

In the introduction to their trial report, Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) [72, p.4] wrote:

There is evidence that it [vitamin C] is of value in pneumonia, particularly in hastening convalescence, and the claims made do not appear to have been contradicted (Gander & Niederberger, 1936 [73]; Vogl, 1937 [74]; Bonnholtzer, 1937 [75]; Hochwald, 1937 [76]; Günzel & Kroehnert, 1937 [77]; Sennewald, 1938; Szirmai, 1940 [78]). Szirmai (1940) noted that while tissue saturation is necessary to obtain maximal benefit in pneumonia, cases of typhoid fever and diphtheria were improved by daily supplements of vitamin C without producing saturation.

In addition to the listed papers in German, benefit from vitamin C for pneumonia was also reported in the USA by Frederick Klenner [79].

Before 1948 there were also reports stating that vitamin C was beneficial against the common cold [80-83]. Though reports of uncontrolled observations do not demonstrate that vitamin C is definitively beneficial for the common cold, they too should have provoked proper consideration of the findings in the placebo-controlled Sheffield study.

The Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) trial included 1435 boarding school boys as participants compared with just 20 participants in the Sheffield study. Glazebrook and Thomson described that they examined boys "*from the lower wage-earning classes*" with "*the food distribution [at the school] was badly managed... Often 8 hr. elapsed between the time the food was cooked and its arrival on the dining tables...*" [72]. The control group received 10-15 mg/day in foods; nevertheless, administration of ~200 mg/day vitamin C had significant effect on various clinically relevant outcomes; see the findings in Appendix 4.

The final Sheffield report wrote about the Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) [72] trial as follows [6, p.44]; see the trial findings in Appendix 2:

In connexion with this result mention should be made of the observation of Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) who studied the incidence and duration of infectious diseases in groups of adolescents living in an institution where the dietary level of vitamin C was very low. The incidence of the common cold and tonsillitis or the average duration of illness due to the common cold was not affected by vitamin C supplements, but the average duration of illness due to tonsillitis was longer in the un-supplemented group.

This is a greatly biased description of the findings in the Glazebrook and Thomson trial; see Appendix 4. The final report could have stated:

Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) found that schoolboys who were administered ~200 mg/day vitamin C had a 23% decrease in the number of common colds needing treatment in the sick quarters ($P < 0.05$), a 57% decrease in days in hospital for patients with streptococcal infections ($P < 0.01$), a 100% decrease in the incidence of pneumonia ($P < 0.01$), a 100% decrease in the incidence of rheumatic fever ($P < 0.01$), and a 50% decrease in “days spent in the sick room per boy due to infective conditions” ($P < 0.00001$). Given that the control group obtained 10-15 mg/day vitamin C in foods, the study findings are very strong evidence against 10 mg/day providing a “sufficient” dose of vitamin C to all children to maintain “full health”.

Thus, the Sheffield study final report ignored many significant benefits from vitamin C in the Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) trial. In addition, the description in the Sheffield report that “*adolescents living in an institution where the dietary level of vitamin C was very low*” is illogical. Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) estimated that dietary vitamin C intake was 10-15 mg/day. The Sheffield study concluded that 10 mg/day of vitamin C is a sufficient dose and logically 10-15 mg/day should also be sufficient and not “very low”.

Appendix 11 shows the findings in the Cowan et al. (1942) trial [84] in the USA which recruited 363 schoolchildren compared with the 20 participants in the Sheffield study. In the Cowan trial, vitamin C intake level in the control group was not estimated, but it is unlikely to have been as low as for the Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) trial. Cowan stated: “*we did no analyses to see whether or not the students were suffering from vitamin deficiency. We assumed that they were not, since most of them were on a reasonably adequate diet*” (p.1271), and Diehl stated: “*the reason for making this study was not that we thought these students exhibited vitamin deficiencies but that the average population is buying millions of dollars’ worth of these vitamins every year*” (p.1271). Thus, there is no basis to assume that food was as poor in vitamin C as the food in the Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) trial.

In the Cowan et al. trial, the supplement of 200 mg/day vitamin C significantly decreased the incidence of colds by 14% and the absence from school by 31%; see Appendix 11. This report, published in JAMA, was ignored in the Sheffield final report [6-8], and in the short summaries [4,5].

Thus, the findings in the Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) trial and the Cowan et al. (1942) trial were inconsistent with the Sheffield study (1953) interpretation that 10 mg/day of vitamin C leads to “full health”, but both controlled trials were not considered in the Sheffield report or the short summaries [4-7].

The low level of vitamin C intake generated in the deprived participants in the Sheffield study (~1 mg/day) is extremely rare in the community. However, research even before the Sheffield study indicated that the effects of vitamin C on infections are not limited to the 1 mg/day vs. 10 mg/day comparison, but there seem to be effects by doses much higher than 10 mg/day. Trials published since the Sheffield study have demonstrated that vitamin C impacts common cold incidence and severity, but the dose-response is complex [85-90].

The common colds of vitamin C deprived subjects lasted longer

The current analysis calculated that vitamin C deprivation increased the duration of colds on average by 77% and decreased the recovery rate from colds by 60% (Fig. 1). In addition, vitamin C deprivation extended the duration of 1-day colds on average by 2.2 days (Fig. 2). These findings are consistent with Jowett's calculations, which led to the conclusion that "*The data support the hypothesis that colds of deprived subjects lasted longer, but do not establish it*".

The Cochrane review on vitamin C and the common cold (2013) pooled the results of 31 placebo-controlled trials in which ≥ 200 mg/day vitamin C was administered regularly over the follow-up period [85,86]. There was very strong evidence that vitamin C shortened the duration of the common colds in the included trials with $P = 0.000\ 000\ 07$ ($Z = 5.28$ [85, Analysis 2.1]).

Thus, the Sheffield study indicated that the duration of colds is an outcome on which vitamin C intake has an effect, and the Cochrane review (2013) confirmed that vitamin C dose has an impact on common cold duration. Nevertheless, the relationship between vitamin C dose and common colds is complex and there seem to be differences in the size of the effect between population groups, life contexts, level of physical stress, and males and females; see e.g. [85,87-92].

The doubling of common cold duration due to vitamin C deprivation in the Sheffield study should have led to explicit suggestions to investigate in more detail the relationship between the vitamin C intake level and the duration of the common cold with larger populations, and with wider ranges of vitamin C intakes, but such encouragement was not published [4-7].

The Lancet summary (1948) defined [4, p.857]:

The term requirement is here used to mean the amount of a dietary essential which must be eaten to maintain full health.

The final Sheffield report (1953) defined [6,7; p.20]:

The term "requirement" is here used to mean the amount of a dietary essential which must be eaten to maintain full health.

Given this definition, it is illogical to ignore the observed doubling of common cold duration during periods of vitamin C deprivation. Shorter duration of colds is relevant to a discussion of "full health". Therefore, the outcome "common cold duration" is important when considering the vitamin C "requirement".

The Sheffield study researchers did not define "scurvy". If scurvy refers to pathological effects caused by vitamin C deficiency, then increased incidence of pneumonia and the common cold, extension of the duration of colds, and the occurrence of cardiac emergencies in 20% of participants are relevant issues. However, it seems that the researchers were primarily interested in the dermatological effects of vitamin C deficiency, which is a very narrow view.

Flawed conclusions about causal effects

The Lancet 1948 summary wrote: “Some other negative findings are worth recording. There was... no increased incidence of infection...” [4, p.854];

“Many signs listed as scorbutic in the classical description of the disease —e.g., pallor, dryness of the skin, anaemia, and night-blindness—were not observed. It is probable that classical scurvy was often a multiple deficiency” [4, p.857].

In the 1953 summary, Krebs wrote: “Negative findings during the period of deprivation included... no increased incidence of infection...” [5, p.240].

“Many signs listed as scorbutic in the classical description of the disease, e.g. pallor, dryness of the skin, anaemia, and night-blindness, were not observed. It is probable that classical scurvy was often a multiple deficiency” [5, p.240].

This is not a valid argument.

First, the number of deprived participants was very small. Only 10 participants were vitamin C deprived while the control group also had just 10 participants. If the frequency of a particular symptom is low, it is missed simply because of the small number of participants. As an illustration of this argument, cigarette smoking increases the risk of lung cancer greatly - by 10-fold. However, if 10 smokers are followed up for a period, it is unlikely that any of them will get lung cancer because the baseline rate is very low. The great majority of smokers don't get lung cancer and observing that no-one in a group of 10 smokers gets lung cancer is not a valid counterargument to the statement that smoking causes lung cancer. Studies require appropriate statistical power, for example, the Doll and Peto (1976) study of British doctors recruited 34,440 men in 1951 and were followed for 2 decades [93] – this study had the power to investigate the effects of cigarette smoking on lung cancer

As to infections, the Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) trial recruited 1435 boarding school boys [72] and the Cowan et al. (1943) trial recruited 363 schoolchildren [84]. The Sheffield study had just 20 participants who were aged 21-34, and not undertaking strenuous physical work. Thus, for the outcome “incidence of infection”, the Sheffield study was minuscule. In addition, the participants in the Sheffield study were not children, and they had a sedentary lifestyle, whereas the majority of schoolchildren in the 1930s and 1940s had a physically active lifestyle. In fact, Glazebrook and Thomson wrote that “Physical training and games occupied much of the day, and it was found that youths at rest in bed required approximately half the quantity of vitamin C, i.e. 2000 mg., to produce full saturation” (p.16). Thus, even if the Sheffield study had been much larger, the participants and contexts were so different that the study might not necessarily have measured the same effects as the 2 trials in schoolchildren.

Second, even if some historical cases of scurvy may have involved multiple vitamin deficiencies, that does not rule out vitamin C deficiency as a contributing cause of their symptoms. For example, in 2 recent case reports of scurvy, patients' hemoglobin levels doubled during vitamin C administration [54,61] clearly indicating that low vitamin C intake was a cause of anemia in these 2 people. Anemia does not need to occur in all people with scurvy for us to conclude that vitamin C deficiency can cause it. Similarly, we can conclude that smoking causes lung cancer, even though only a subset of smokers develop the disease. In addition, the emergence of anemia might require other simultaneous factors, but the simultaneous factors do not refute that vitamin C deficiency can be a cause of anemia. Rothman and Greenland formulated this issue as follows [94, p.S145]:

The importance of multicausality is that most identified causes are neither necessary nor sufficient to produce disease. Nevertheless, a cause need not be either necessary or sufficient for its removal to result in disease prevention. If a component cause that is neither necessary nor sufficient is blocked, a substantial amount of disease may be prevented. That the cause is not necessary implies that some disease may still occur after the cause is blocked, but a component cause will nevertheless be a necessary cause for some of the cases that occur. That the component cause is not sufficient implies that other component causes must interact with it to produce the disease, and that blocking any of them would result in prevention of some cases of disease. Thus, one need not identify every component cause to prevent some cases of disease. In the law, a distinction is sometimes made among component causes to identify those that may be considered a “proximate” cause, implying a more direct connection or responsibility for the outcome.

The Sheffield study has had great influence on the vitamin C recommendation in the UK¹

The current (2025) UK nutritional recommendations for vitamin C were formulated in 1991 [95], with the Sheffield study being the first reference. However, the UK recommendation does not mention that colds were twice as long in vitamin C deprived participants in the Sheffield study. Neither does the recommendation mention the Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) trial even though it was 71-fold larger than the Sheffield study, was also carried out in the UK, and found significant benefit from vitamin C administration to schoolchildren who had baseline vitamin C intake above the level of the assumed requirement of 10 mg/day.

Furthermore, after the publication of the Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) trial and the Sheffield (1953) study there were several further placebo-controlled trials in the UK before 1991 that found vitamin C to be beneficial for the common cold, i.e., indicating that ordinary diets in the UK may have been too low in vitamin C to maintain full health for all of the population; see **Appendix 12**.

A systematic review published in 1992 identified 18 placebo-controlled trials and all of them found shorter duration or less severity of colds in groups administered ≥ 1 g/day of vitamin C compared with the placebo groups, with $P = 0.000\ 004$ in a binomial distribution [96]. All of these 18 trials were published before 1991, and all were not considered in the UK recommendations.

Another systematic review published in 1997 showed that vitamin C administration decreased the incidence of colds in 4 trials with British males, on average, by 30% ($P = 0.000\ 001$) [97]. In addition, one study with British males found that 4 g/day vitamin C treatment of the first cold reduced recurrent colds by 40% ($P = 0.018$) [98], and another found that 1 g/day vitamin C decreased the incidence of “chest colds” in British females by 18% ($P = 0.014$) [99]. See Appendix 12 for the positive findings in the UK trials between 1953 and 1991. These trials would seem to appear particularly relevant when considering vitamin C intake levels in the UK. However, these trials were also ignored in the UK recommendations [95].

Chris Bates criticized the 1997 meta-analysis [97,100]. He was the Vice-Chairman of the Panel on Dietary Reference Values Working Group on Vitamins, and a Member of the Committee on Medical Aspects of Food Policy Panel on Dietary Reference Values for the 1991 recommendations [95]. However, Hemilä addressed the criticism point by point [100].

¹ A longer version of this critique was published as:
Hemilä H, Chalker E. Are the UK’s Vitamin C Recommendations Evidence-Based? A Critical Comment.
Br J Nutr. 2025 Dec 22. doi: 10.1017/S0007114525105941.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/41424103>

Bias against vitamins

Given that the Sheffield report published Jowett's conclusion "*Such evidence as there is, however, definitely confirms the hypothesis that the absence of vitamin C tended to cause colds to last longer... The data support the hypothesis that colds of deprived subjects lasted longer, but do not establish it*", it is puzzling that this was ignored in the full report [6-8], in the summaries [4,5], and in the UK vitamin C recommendation (1991) [95]. As described above, this was not an isolated observation, instead there were many positive reports on the effects of vitamin C against respiratory infections after the pure substance became available in the 1930s [73-83,101-103]. In addition, a few controlled trials reported benefit from vitamin C administration before the Sheffield study; see Appendix 4 and 11.

A long time ago, vitamin C deficiency was identified as the explanation for scurvy, which was largely considered a disease of connective tissues. This is illustrated also by the focus of the Sheffield study, with the main interest being on the timing and scope of "enlargement and keratosis of the hair follicles" [item 2 in Appendix 1] and the recovery of wounds. It seems that the 20% incidence of cardiac emergencies, the 10% incidence of tuberculosis, and the 10% incidence of effusions in a knee joint were considered more as nuisances that interfered with the dermatological observations in the Sheffield study, rather than as clinically significant findings with far greater implications for overall population health.

Evidently, it seemed illogical to consider that a substance that participates 'only' in connective tissue metabolism might also have effects on the common cold, which may explain that the observations on common cold duration were also ignored. This background may partly explain the rejection of the series of positive findings on vitamin C for infections over decades [104-107]. There can also be socio-political roots to the bias against vitamin C supplements, see **Appendix 13**.

Conclusions

The Sheffield study found that vitamin C deprivation nearly doubled the duration of colds. The reanalysis in this paper found that vitamin C deprivation increased the duration of colds on average by 77% and decreased the recovery rate from colds by 60%. Intake of vitamin C in the deprived participants was particularly low (~1 mg/day) and such levels are very rare. However, there was no basis to assume that the effect of vitamin C on the common cold in the Sheffield study was limited to the very low dose range. In fact, 2 placebo-controlled trials carried out prior to the Sheffield study had already shown significant benefits of vitamin C for schoolchildren even though their baseline intake was higher than the deprivation level in the Sheffield study. Despite this, these earlier findings were omitted from the 179-page final report and from the two major summaries of the Sheffield study. While the 2 cases of cardiac emergencies among the 10 scurvy patients were mentioned, they were downplayed, and no recommendation was made to further investigate the effects of low vitamin C intake on cardiac function. This apparent bias against the positive findings related to the common cold and heart function may stem from the narrow focus on dermatological outcomes, despite the well-established fact that vitamin C has important effects beyond the skin.

Acknowledgments. The author is grateful to Elizabeth Chalker for critically reading the manuscript.

References to the Sheffield study are listed on page 6.

Other references:

17. Number needed to harm. *Wikipedia*.
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Number_needed_to_harm
18. Mendes D, Alves C, Batel-Marques F. Number needed to treat (NNT) in clinical literature: an appraisal. *BMC Med*. 2017;15(1):112.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28571585>
19. Callaway B. Quantile Treatment Effects in R: The qte Package (2022-08-31). *R project*.
<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/qte/vignettes/R-QTEs.html>
20. Hemilä H, Chalker E, Tukiainen J. Quantile treatment effect of zinc lozenges on common cold duration: a novel approach to analyze the effect of treatment on illness duration. *Front Pharmacol*. 2022;13:817522.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.817522>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8844493>
21. Hemilä H, Chalker E, Tukiainen J. Response: Commentary: Quantile treatment effect of zinc lozenges on common cold duration: a novel approach to analyze the effect of treatment on illness duration. *Front Pharmacol*. 2024;15:1335784.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2024.1335784>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC11035776>
22. Hemilä H, Pirinen M. Estimating quantile treatment effect on the original scale of the outcome variable: a case study of common cold treatments. *Trials*. 2025;26:541.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-025-09265-z>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC12645726>
23. Pirinen M, Hemilä H. bqte: R code to estimate back-transformed quantile treatment [computer program, version 2025-8]. *GitHub*.
<https://github.com/mjpirinen/bqte>
24. Hemilä H, Carr A, Chalker E. Vitamin C may increase the recovery rate of outpatient cases of SARS-CoV-2 infection by 70%: reanalysis of the COVID A to Z randomized clinical trial. *Front Immunol*. 2021;12:674681.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.674681>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8141621>
25. Bootstrapping (statistics). *Wikipedia*.
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bootstrapping_\(statistics\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bootstrapping_(statistics))
26. Lind J. *A Treatise on the Scurvy in Three Parts. A Treatise on the Scurvy, in Three Parts. Containing an Inquiry into the Nature, Causes, and Cure, of that Disease. Together with a Critical and Chronological View of what has been published on the Subject. The Second Edition.* 1757.
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/xc2t7736/items?canvas=161> [p.137: Krebs extract “Persons...”]
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/xc2t7736/items?canvas=9> [p.v-vi: Hawkins]²
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/xc2t7736/items?canvas=459> [p.435: Anson]³
<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy00lind/page/n164/mode/1up> [p.137 Krebs extract]
<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy00lind/page/n10/mode/1up> [p.v-vi: Hawkins]
<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy00lind/page/n462/mode/1up> [p.435: Anson]
See selected extracts of Lind’s texts in Ref. 28 below.

2 Scurvy during Richard Hawkins' voyage (1593)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001137>

3 Scurvy on Anson's voyage round the world (1740-1744)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17397300>

27. Drummond JC, Wilbraham A. William Stark, M.D.: an eighteenth century experiment in nutrition. *Lancet*. 1935;226:459–63.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(00\)94709-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(00)94709-3)
<https://doi.org/10.1177/096777200000800304>
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/William_Stark_\(physician\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/William_Stark_(physician))
<https://archive.org/details/b21441200/page/n3/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/workslatewilli00star/page/n5/mode/2up>
https://archive.org/details/bim_eighteenth-century_the-works-of-stark-william
28. Hemilä H. The symptoms of vitamin C deficiency.
 1. Observations and descriptions by Hess, Lind, Trotter and Blane. *Zenodo*. 2024.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194>
29. Budd G. Scurvy. In: *The Library of Medicine; The System of Practical Medicine*. Ed. Tweedie A. 1840;5:58-95.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17455962>
https://archive.org/details/b33096314_0005/page/58/mode/2up
See other early reports on scurvy at:
 Reports on scurvy uploaded to *Zenodo* by Harri Hemilä.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738>
30. Seidlitz. On haemorrhagic pericarditis. *British and Foreign Medical Review*. 1836;1(1):259–63.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11175282>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5556493/?page=12>
<https://archive.org/details/s2571id1380017/page/258/mode/2up>
31. Kyber A. On pericarditis scorbutica, and its treatment by paracentesis. *Ranking's Abstract*. 1848;7:64-5.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11175404>
<https://books.google.fi/books?id=nPJYAAAAMAAJ>
32. Darling S. The pathologic affinities of beriberi and scurvy. *JAMA*. 1914;63(15):1290-4.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10102994>
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1914.02570150046011>
33. Hess AF. Cardiorespiratory involvement in infantile scurvy. *Proc Soc Exp Biol Med*. 1916;14(1):4-5.
<https://doi.org/10.3181/00379727-14-3>
<https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/156376#page/14/mode/1up>
34. Hess AF. Subacute and latent infantile scurvy: the cardiorespiratory syndrome (a new sign). *JAMA*. 1917;68(4):235-9.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10102042>
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1917.04270010235001>
35. Erdheim J. The heart in infantile scurvy [Über das Barlow-Herz; in German; translated to English]. *Wiener Klinische Wochenschrift*. 1918;31(49):1293-5.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7756493>
36. Bierich R. Scurvy [Über Skorbut; in German; translated to English]. *Deutsches Archiv Für Klinische Medizin*. 1919;130(26 Sept):151-71.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10653559>
<https://archive.org/details/deutschesarchivfurklinischemedizin.v.129130.1919/page/n547/mode/2up>
37. Comrie JD. Scurvy in North Russia. *Edinb Med J*. 1920;24(4):207-15.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5294660>
38. Swarbreck A. Avitaminosis. *Br Med J*. 1932;2:123.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.2.3732.123>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2521146>
39. Barton WE, Freeman W. Pericardial hemorrhage complicating scurvy. *N Engl J Med*. 1934;210(10):529-31.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10103536>
<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM193403082101005>

40. Platt R. Scurvy as the result of dietetic treatment. *Lancet*. 1936;228:366-7.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(00\)48407-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(00)48407-2)
41. Evans W. Vitamin C in heart failure. *Lancet*. 1938;231:308-9.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(00\)62412-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(00)62412-1)
42. Follis RH. Sudden death in infants with scurvy. *J Pediatr*. 1942;20(3):347-51.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3476\(42\)80190-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3476(42)80190-0)
43. Shaffer CF. The diuretics effect of ascorbic acid: preliminary report on its use in cardiac decompensation. *JAMA*. 1944;124(11):700-1.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10103113>
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1944.02850110024006>
44. Hess AF. *Scurvy: Past and Present*. Lippincott; Philadelphia, PA, 1920.
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>
<https://digital.library.cornell.edu/catalog/chla2903792>
<https://archive.org/search?query=creator%3A%22Hess+Alfred%22+scurvy>
See biographies:
<https://doi.org/10.1053/j.spid.2005.01.003>
<https://doi.org/10.1007/bf01955048>
<https://doi.org/10.2105/ajph.65.9.977>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1775957>
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/71.1.1>
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-3476\(55\)80182-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-3476(55)80182-5)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1965595>
<https://doi.org/10.1001/archpedi.1934.01960100161022>
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.79.2039.70>
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/1660244>
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alfred_Fabian_Hess
45. *Medical and surgical history of the British Army: which served in Turkey and the Crimea during the war against Russia in the years 1854-55-56 (Volume 2)*. London, UK, 1858.
<https://zenodo.org/records/10103880> [section on scurvy]
<https://archive.org/details/62510370RX2.nlm.nih.gov/page/n193/mode/2up>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=nnc1.cu04838203&seq=193>
46. Hemilä H, Suonsyrjä T. Vitamin C for preventing atrial fibrillation in high risk patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Cardiovasc Disord*. 2017;17(1):49.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12872-017-0478-5>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5286679>
47. Hemilä H, Chalker E, de Man AME. Vitamin C may improve left ventricular ejection fraction: a meta-analysis. *Front Cardiovasc Med*. 2022;9:789729.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fcvm.2022.789729>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8913583>
48. Rozemeijer S, Hemilä H, van Baaren M, de Man AME. Vitamin C may reduce troponin and CKMB levels after PCI and CABG: a meta-analysis. *BMC Cardiovasc Disord*. 2023;23(1):475.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12872-023-03459-6>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10512653>
49. Hemilä H, de Man AME. Vitamin C deficiency can lead to pulmonary hypertension: a systematic review of case reports. *BMC Pulm Med*. 2024;24(1):140.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12890-024-02941-x>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10949735>
50. Shafar J. Rapid reversion of electrocardiographic abnormalities after treatment in two cases of scurvy. *Lancet*. 1967;290:176-8.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(67\)90004-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(67)90004-9)
51. Singh D, Chan W. Cardiomegaly and generalized oedema due to vitamin C deficiency. *Singapore Med J*. 1974;15:60-3.
<https://smj.sma.org.sg/1501/1501smj11.pdf>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4276407>

52. Meisel JL, McDowell RK. Case 39-1995: a 72-year-old man with exertional dyspnea, fatigue, and extensive ecchymoses and purpuric lesions. *N Engl J Med*. 1995;333:1695-702.
<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM199512213332508>
53. Kieffer P, Thannberger P, Wilhelm JM, Kieffer C, Schneider F. Multiple organ dysfunction dramatically improving with the infusion of vitamin C: more support for the persistence of scurvy in our welfare society. *Intensive Care Med*. 2001;27(2):448.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s001340000830>
54. Kupari M, Rapola J. Reversible pulmonary hypertension associated with vitamin C deficiency. *Chest*. 2012;142(1):225-7.
<https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.11-1857>
55. Abbas F, Ha LD, Sterns R, von Doenhoff L. Reversible right heart failure in scurvy: rediscovery of an old observation. *Circ Heart Fail*. 2016;9(10):e003497.
<https://doi.org/10.1161/circheartfailure.116.003497>
56. Bennett SE, Schmitt WP, Stanford FC, Baron JM. Case 22-2018: a 64-year-old man with progressive leg weakness, recurrent falls, and anemia. *N Engl J Med*. 2018;379:282-9.
<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMcp1802826>
57. Alnaimat S, Oseni A, Yang Y, Melvani V, Aronson A, Harris K, Panaich S. Missing vitamin C: a case of scorbutic cardiac tamponade. *JACC Case Rep*. 2019;1(2):192-6.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccas.2019.07.006>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8301525>
58. Penn EH, Olenchock BA, Marston NA. A shocking deficiency. *Circulation*. 2019;140:613-7.
<https://doi.org/10.1161/circulationaha.119.040894>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6812570>
59. Gayen SK, Abdelrahman AA, Preston IR, Petit RD, Hill NS. Vitamin C deficiency-induced pulmonary arterial hypertension. *Chest*. 2020;157(2):e21-3.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chest.2019.06.043>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339025620>
60. Flanagan LS, Sadek A, Oliveros E. Vitamin C deficiency as a readily reversible cause of pulmonary hypertension. *JACC Case Rep*. 2025;30:103424.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccas.2025.103424>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC12235451>
61. Ueki M, Sakamoto K, Nishioka N, et al. Rheumatologic manifestations with elevated levels of IL-6, IL-17A, and IL-23 in a patient with scurvy. *Mod Rheumatol Case Rep*. 2023;7:302-6.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/mrcr/rxac059>
62. Allender WJ. Post mortem tissue levels of ascorbic acid in a scurvy case. *J Anal Toxicol*. 1982;6(4):202-4.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jat/6.4.202>
63. Maltos AL, Portari GV, Saldanha JC, Bernardes Júnior AG, Pardi GR, da Cunha DF. Scurvy in an alcoholic malnourished cirrhotic man with spontaneous bacterial peritonitis. *Clin (Sao Paulo)*. 2012;67(4):405-7.
[https://doi.org/10.6061/clinics/2012\(04\)16](https://doi.org/10.6061/clinics/2012(04)16)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3317255>
64. Doll S, Ricou B. Severe vitamin C deficiency in a critically ill adult: a case report. *Eur J Clin Nutr*. 2013;67(8):881-2.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/ejcn.2013.42>
65. Azar J, Varasteh A, Iltchev D, Soliman M, Baez V, Altaqi B. A very uncommon case of pulmonary arterial hypertension. *Am J Med Case Rep*. 2019;7(5):79-86.
<https://doi.org/10.12691/ajmcr-7-5-2>
66. Hashizume H, Ishikawa Y, Ajima S. Modern scurvy revisited: Japanese cases of a forgotten disease. *J Dermatol*. 2023;50(11):e388-9.

- <https://doi.org/10.1111/1346-8138.16891>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372619162>
67. Barlow T. The Bradshaw lecture on infantile scurvy and its relation to rickets: delivered before the Royal College of Physicians of London.
Br Med J. 1894;2(1767):1029-34.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.2.1767.1029>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2405492>
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/20230441>
Lancet. 1894;144:1075-80.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(01\)93995-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(01)93995-9)
Original versions:
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/um6f7sfm>
<https://archive.org/details/b24905847>
See biographies:
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1935.02760410037015>
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.287.6408.1862>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1550031>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc2056559>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1987940>
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s002572730005849x>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1036751>
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-3476\(57\)80317-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-3476(57)80317-5)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1561482>
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sir_Thomas_Barlow,_1st_Baronet
68. Hess AF. Infantile scurvy. Part V. A study of its pathogenesis. *Am J Dis Child.* 1917;14:337-53.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609522>
<https://doi.org/10.1001/archpedi.1917.01910110018002>
69. Hess AF. Diet, nutrition and infection. *N Engl J Med.* 1932;207:637-48.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609616> [section on vitamin C and infections]
<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM193210132071501>
70. Hess AF. Recent advances in knowledge of scurvy and the antiscorbutic vitamin.
JAMA. 1932;98(17):1429-33.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609694> [section on vitamin C and infections]
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1932.02730430005002>
71. Sabin AB. Vitamin C in relation to experimental poliomyelitis: with incidental observations on certain manifestations in Macacus rhesus monkeys on a scorbutic diet.
J Exp Med. 1939;69(4):507-16.
<https://doi.org/10.1084/jem.69.4.507>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2133652>
See biographies:
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19008524>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21719614>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8888238>
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Albert_Sabin
72. Glazebrook AJ, Thomson S. The administration of vitamin C in a large institution and its effect on general health and resistance to infection. *J Hyg (Lond).* 1942;42:1-19.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0022172400012596>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2199803>
73. Gander J, Niederberger J. Vitamin C in the treatment of pneumonia [Vitamin C in der Pneumonie-Behandlung; in German; translation available].
Munch Med Wochenschr. 1936;83:2074-7.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6406760>
74. Vogl A. Erfahrungen über die Behandlung der Lungenentzündung mit C-vitamin [In German].
Münchener Medizinische Wochenschrift. 1937;84:1569-72.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15202539>

75. Bohnholtzer E. Contribution to the question of pneumonia treatment with vitamin C [Beitrag zur Frage der Pneumoniebehandlung mit Vitamin C; in German; translation available]. *Dtsch Med Wochenschr.* 1937;63:1001-3.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6406564>
<https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0028-1121197> [in German]
76. Hochwald A. Vitamin C in the treatment of croupous pneumonia [Vitamin C in der Behandlung der kruppösen Pneumonie; in German; translation available]. *Dtsch Med Wochenschr.* 1937;63:182-4.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6406698>
<https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0028-1120960> [in German]
77. Günzel W, Kroehnert G. Erfahrungen mit Vitamin C in der Pneumoniebehandlung [in German]. *Fortschritte der Therapie.* 1937;11(8):460-3.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10933116>
78. Szirmai F. Über den Wert des C-Vitamins in der Behandlung einzelner akuter Infektionskrankheiten [in German]. *Deutsches Archiv für klinische Medizin.* 1940;185:434-43.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15202715>
79. Klenner FR. Virus pneumonia and its treatment with vitamin C. *South Med Surg.* 1948;110(2):36-8.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10932789>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18900646>
80. Ruskin SL. Calcium cevitamate in the treatment of acute rhinitis. *Ann Otol Rhinol Laryngol.* 1938;47:502-11.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14494040>
<https://doi.org/10.1177/000348943804700218>
81. Korbsch R. About the curtailing of inflammatory allergic states through L-ascorbic acid [Über die Kupierung entzündlich-allergischer Zustände durch die l-Askorbinsäure; in German; translation available]. *Medizinische Klinik.* 1938;34:1500-1.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6513819>
82. Brown WB, Mahoney F, Niedringhaus A, Locke A. Weather and susceptibility in relation to the spread of common cold; effect of ascorbic acid, in massive dosage, on duration. *J Immunol.* 1945;50:161-77.
<https://doi.org/10.4049/jimmunol.50.3.161>
83. Markwell NW. Vitamin C in the prevention of colds. *Med J Australia.* 1947;2:777-8.
<https://doi.org/10.5694/j.1326-5377.1947.tb74386.x>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18899197>
84. Cowan DW, Diehl HS, Baker AB. Vitamins for the prevention of colds. *JAMA.* 1942;120(16):1268-71.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14674396>
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1942.02830510006002>
85. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C for preventing and treating the common cold. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2013;2013:CD000980.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8078152>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225864>
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd000980.pub4>
<https://www.mv.helsinki.fi/home/hemila/CC> [Links to references]
86. Shamseer L, Vohra S, Bax R, Spee L, Madderom M, Hemilä H. Commentaries on 'Vitamin C for preventing and treating the common cold' with responses from the review author. *Evid Based Child Health: A Cochrane Rev J.* 2008;3:723-8.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228088>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/244785237>
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ebch.261>
87. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C reduces the severity of common colds: a meta-analysis. *BMC Public Health.* 2023;23:2468.

- <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-17229-8>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10712193>
88. Hemilä H. Vitamin C supplementation and common cold symptoms: factors affecting the magnitude of the benefit. *Med Hypotheses*. 1999;52:171-8.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/223761>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/12959141>
<https://doi.org/10.1054/mehy.1997.0639>
89. Hemilä H. Vitamin C and infections. *Nutrients*. 2017;9(4):339.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu9040339>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5409678>
90. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C for the common cold and pneumonia. *Pol Arch Intern Med*. 2025;135(1):16926.
<https://doi.org/10.20452/pamw.16926>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/39803741>
91. Hemilä H. Vitamin C and sex differences in respiratory tract infections. *Respir Med*. 2008; 102: 625-626.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rmed.2007.12.011>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228090>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/5628489>
92. Constantini NW, Dubnov-Raz G, Eyal BB, Berry EM, Cohen AH, Hemilä H. The effect of vitamin C on upper respiratory infections in adolescent swimmers: a randomized trial. *Eur J Pediatr*. 2011;170(1):59-63.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228085>
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00431-010-1270-z>
93. Doll R, Peto R. Mortality in relation to smoking: 20 years' observations on male British doctors. *Br Med J*. 1976;2(6051):1525-36.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1690096>
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.2.6051.1525>
94. Rothman KJ, Greenland S. Causation and causal inference in epidemiology. *Am J Public Health*. 2005;95(Suppl 1):S144-S150.
<https://doi.org/10.2105/ajph.2004.059204>
95. Vitamin C. In: Dietary reference values for food energy and nutrients for the United Kingdom. Report of the Panel on Dietary Reference Values of the Committee on Medical Aspects of Food Policy. *Rep Health Soc Subj (Lond)*. 1991;41:117-22.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13946536> [section on vitamin C]
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/pguqct9n/items?canvas=145>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1961974>
- 95a. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Are the UK's vitamin C recommendations evidence-based? A critical comment. *Br J Nutr*. 2025 Dec 22. doi: 10.1017/S0007114525105941. Epub ahead of print.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0007114525105941>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/41424103>
96. Hemilä H. Vitamin C and the common cold. *Br J Nutr*. 1992;67(1):3-16.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/223363>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259425819>
<https://doi.org/10.1079/bjn19920004>
97. Hemilä H. Vitamin C intake and susceptibility to the common cold. *Br J Nutr*. 1997;77:59-72.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/223362>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/14153016>
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0007114500002889>
98. Tyrrell DA, Craig JW, Meada TW, White T. A trial of ascorbic acid in the treatment of the common cold. *Br J Prev Soc Med*. 1977;31:189-91.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC479021>
<https://doi.org/10.1136/jech.31.3.189>
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/25565969>

99. Elwood PC, Lee HP, St Leger AS, Baird M, Howard AN. A randomized controlled trial of vitamin C in the prevention and amelioration of the common cold. *Br J Prev Soc Med.* 1976;30:193-6.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC478963>
<https://doi.org/10.1136/jech.30.3.193>
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/25565911>
100. Bates CJ, Schorah CJ, Hemilä H. Vitamin C intake and susceptibility to the common cold: Invited commentaries and response. *Br J Nutr.* 1998;78:857-66.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/223364>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14610440>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/28369859>
<https://doi.org/10.1079/BJN19970201>
101. Robertson E C. The vitamins and resistance to infection. *Medicine.* 1934;13(3):123-206.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14496927> [sections on vitamin C and infections]
<https://doi.org/10.1097/00005792-193405000-00001>
102. Clausen S. The influence of nutrition upon resistance to infection. *Physiological Reviews.* 1934;14(3):309-50.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14525720> [sections on vitamin C and infections]
<https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.1934.14.3.309>
103. Perla D, Marmorston J. Role of vitamin C in resistance. *Archives of Pathology.* 1937;23:543-75,683-712.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14527877>
104. Hemilä H. Vitamin C supplementation and common cold symptoms: problems with inaccurate reviews. *Nutrition.* 1996;12(11-12):804-9.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225877>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/263724831>
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0899-9007\(96\)00223-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0899-9007(96)00223-7)
105. Hemilä H, Herman ZS. Vitamin C and the common cold: a retrospective analysis of Chalmers' review. *J Am Coll Nutr.* 1995;14(2):116-23.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/42358>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/15407891>
<https://doi.org/10.1080/07315724.1995.10718483>
Biographies of Thomas Chalmers:
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26880652>
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1996.03540080078041>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1335248>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1335469>
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0197-2456\(96\)90026-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0197-2456(96)90026-4)
<https://circulatingnow.nlm.nih.gov/2014/12/18/thomas-c-chalmers-clinical-research-pragmatist/>
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thomas_C._Chalmers
106. Hemilä H. Vitamin C, the placebo effect, and the common cold: a case study of how preconceptions influence the analysis of results. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 1996;49(10):1079-84; discussion 1085, 1087.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225872>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/14378347>
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(96\)00189-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(96)00189-8)
See discussion:
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(96\)00190-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(96)00190-4)
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(96\)00191-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(96)00191-6)
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225873>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/28363121>
107. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Bias against vitamin C in mainstream medicine: examples from trials of vitamin C for infections. *Life (Basel).* 2022;12(1):62.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/life12010062>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8779885>

Appendix 1: Summary of the Sheffield study [6,7; pp.143-144]

The Summary is available also at the Zenodo repository:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14628064>

1. Twenty volunteers were given a diet containing less than 1 mg. vitamin C daily. Three received a vitamin C supplement of 70 mg. daily, seven received 10 mg. and ten had no supplement. No signs of deficiency were observed in those receiving supplements during a period of observation of up to 14 months.
2. All ten volunteers receiving no supplement developed clinical signs of scurvy, though in varying degree. The first changes were enlargement and keratosis of the hair follicles, beginning after 17 weeks of deprivation. Later the enlarged hair follicles became haemorrhagic and formed the characteristic scorbutic spots. Scorbutic gum changes began to appear after 26 weeks of deprivation.
3. Five of the ten deprived volunteers showed a very pronounced exacerbation of the acne present in a mild form at the start of the trial. The exacerbation began after about 22 weeks of deprivation.
4. In one case effusion into both knee joints and ecchymoses of the leg occurred, and two volunteers developed cardiac complications which are described and discussed.
5. A dose of 10 mg. of vitamin C daily given to six of the scorbutic volunteers removed the clinical signs of scurvy in all cases. Within 1 or 2 weeks the scorbutic spots began to fade and within from 7 to 9 weeks the appearance of the skin became normal. The gum lesions responded more slowly, restoration being complete within from 10 to 14 weeks.
6. The volunteers receiving a 70 mg. supplement maintained the initial vitamin C level of the plasma which on an average was 0.55 mg. per 100 ml. In the totally deprived volunteers the vitamin C level of the plasma fell rapidly, reaching about 0.03 mg. per 100 ml. after 37 days and remaining below this value for the rest of the deprivation period. In the volunteers receiving a supplement of 10 mg. the plasma level of vitamin C was of the same order throughout as in the totally deprived group. Thus a difference in the vitamin C intake of 10 mg. daily (enough to prevent and cure clinical scurvy) was not reflected in differences in the plasma level of vitamin C.
7. The volunteers receiving a 70 mg. supplement maintained the initial vitamin C level of the white blood cells which on an average was 16.6 mg. per 100 g. In the totally deprived volunteers the vitamin C level of the white blood cells fell to 1 mg. per 100 g. in 113 days, remaining below this value for the rest of the deprivation period. In the volunteers receiving a supplement of 10 mg. the vitamin C level in the white cells also fell but remained roughly 1 mg. per 100 g. above the value for the deficient group.

8. In the deprived group there was no change in body weight and no increased incidence of infection although colds seemed to last longer. Dark adaptation measurements and audiometry gave no abnormal results. The haemoglobin concentration, red cell count, white cell count and bleeding time showed no significant changes.

9. Conventional tests of so-called capillary strength failed to show correlation with the state of vitamin C depletion.

10. Pains in the back, joints and limbs were reported with increasing frequency by the depleted volunteers as the signs of scurvy developed.

11. No significant variations from normal were observed in the plasma values for protein, urea or phosphatase, or in the albumin-globulin ratio.

12. Experimental wounds were made with the object of studying the process of wound healing. The scars left after such wounds had been excised became haemorrhagic at the height of scurvy. Examination of scar tissue by histological methods and breaking-strain tests gave abnormal findings in the deprived group but not in the two groups receiving a supplement.

13. Saturation tests carried out towards the end of the experiment differentiated between vitamin C intakes above 20 mg. but not between the levels so important in practice of 20 mg. and below. An intake of 10 or 20 mg. (sufficient to cure and prevent scurvy) gave about the same result as an intake of 5 mg. (which is below the safety level).

14. Administration to scorbutic volunteers of a tyrosine supplement, which increased the normal daily tyrosine intake from about 5-6 g. to 25 g., did not lead to an increase in urinary excretion of tyrosine and its derivatives as measured by the phenol test of Folin and Ciocalteu.

15. The changes in the capillaries round the hair follicles were examined by capillaroscopy and are described in detail.

16. The urine of deprived volunteers when the true vitamin C content must have been near zero was used for testing the specificity of vitamin C estimations. Direct titration with 2:6-dichlorophenolindophenol gave values between 13 and 48 mg. It is pointed out that the quantity of material behaving like vitamin C in this method is likely to vary with the diet. The dinitrophenylhydrazine method of Roe and Kuether and the dichlorophenolindophenol-formaldehyde method are more specific, but interfering substances simulating vitamin C were still not completely eliminated.

17. The vitamin C requirements of human adults are considered in the light of the results of the present trial. The fact that a supplement of 10 mg. daily cured clinical scurvy in all six cases examined, together with the observation that 10 mg. daily protected seven volunteers for periods of up to 424 days, are taken to indicate that in the group under test the minimum protective dose of vitamin C, measured by the presence or absence of the signs of scurvy, was in the region of 10 mg. daily. In order to arrive at a figure for a daily allowance which covers individual variations and includes a safety margin, it is suggested that the minimum protective dose of 10 mg. be trebled. An allowance of 30 mg. daily is in accordance with the recommendation by the League of Nations Health Organisation Technical Commission on Nutrition made in 1938.

INCIDENCE AND DURATION OF COLDS

Throughout the experiment the volunteers recorded the number and duration of the colds they experienced. These data are presented in Table 44 (p. 134). At a glance they seemed to indicate that the average number of colds in the deprived and non-deprived groups did not differ markedly, but that they lasted longer in the deprived group. The material was accordingly submitted to a statistician (C. H. Jowett) for analysis, who summarized his investigation as follows:

“The lengths of all colds were subjected to the transformation $y = 20 \log x$. It was considered that this would make the various distributions on which the statistical tests depended more close to ‘normal’. The data analysed consisted of the following:

Colds of members of deprived group before dosing.

Colds of members of supplemented group up to and including July 1945.

Assuming for the moment that time of year had no appreciable effect, the following conclusions emerged from the analysis of variance given in Table 18.

TABLE 18

Analysis of variance of transformed lengths of colds

Source of variation	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean square
Difference between groups	431.8	1	431.8 (1)
Differences between individuals within a group ..	1092.1	10	109.2 (2)
Variation of length of cold within an individual ..	1365.8	27	50.6 (3)

The ratio of the mean squares (2)/(3) fell just short of the 5 per cent level of significance, but since it almost attained that level, and moreover for *a priori* reasons, it was considered that differences between individuals did in fact exist; the mean square (1) was accordingly tested against (2), the ratio (1)/(2) being equal to 3.95. This value lies between the 5 per cent level and the 10 per cent level of significance, and hence there is no conclusive evidence of a difference between mean transformed length of colds from supplemented to deprived groups. Such evidence as there is, however, definitely confirms the hypothesis that the absence of vitamin C tended to cause colds to last longer.

The geometric mean length of colds of non-deprived subjects = 3.3 days (4)

The geometric mean length of colds of deprived subjects = 6.4 days (5)

As a further check the seasonal difference in colds was investigated; differences between season lengths were not marked, and the numbers of winter and summer colds did not differ seriously from group to group. It may safely be concluded that the difference between the means (4) and (5) was not a manifestation of the seasonal effect.

In illustration of the seasonal differences, the geometric mean lengths of colds for the ‘winter’ months and the ‘early summer’ months are given in Table 19.

TABLE 19

Seasonal incidence and duration of colds

Season	Geometric mean length in group:		No. of colds in group	
	supplemented (days)	deprived (days)	supplemented	deprived
November–February	4.0	7.6	11	8
April–July	3.2	7.2	8	8

Conclusion

The data support the hypothesis that colds of deprived subjects lasted longer, but do not establish it.”

In connexion with this result mention should be made of the observation of Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) who studied the incidence and duration of infectious diseases in groups of adolescents living in an institution where the dietary level of vitamin C was very low. The incidence of the common cold and tonsillitis or the average duration of illness due to the common cold was not affected by vitamin C supplements, but the average duration of illness due to tonsillitis was longer in the unsupplemented group.

DIET DURING THE PRELIMINARY PERIOD

Base line data for fifteen of the volunteers were collected for a preliminary period of 6 weeks, during which they consumed an ordinary diet containing about 60 mg. vitamin C daily from natural sources. Apples were used to adjust the vitamin C intake to that level. The other five volunteers joined the team a few weeks later and they were given, for the preliminary period, the basal diet with a supplement of 70 mg. vitamin C daily. Details are given in Table 30.

TABLE 30

Duration of the preliminary period, and the periods of administration and amounts of vitamin C supplements received by the volunteers

Name	Period on preliminary diet* (days)	Vitamin C supplement (mg. daily)	Period on supplement	
			Dates	No. of days
Bartley ..	42	70	13.11.44 to 7. 9.45	299
Drake ..	42	0	13.11.44 to 3. 7.45	233
		10	4. 7.45 to 4.11.45	124
		20	5.11.45 to 3. 1.46	60
		510	4. 1.46 to 14. 1.46	11
Garling ..	42	70	13.11.44 to 3.10.45	325
		50	4.10.45 to 10.12.45	68
		630	11.12.45 to 19.12.45	9
Golding ..	42	10	13.11.44 to 8. 1.46	422
		570	9. 1.46 to 18. 1.46	10
Hill	42	70	13.11.44 to 7.10.45	329
		50	8.10.45 to 10.12.45	64
		630	11.12.45 to 19.12.45	10
Hudson ..	42	0	13.11.44 to 30. 7.45	260
		10	31. 7.45 to 18.11.45	111
		20	19.11.45 to 3. 1.46	46
		670	4. 1.46 to 13. 1.46	10
Jackson ..	14	0	11.12.44 to 17.12.44	7
		10	18.12.44 to 27. 5.45	161
		0	28. 5.45 to 7. 8.45	71
		5	8. 8.45 to 10.12.45	125
		630	11.12.45 to 19.12.45	9
Milburn ..	42	0	13.11.44 to 20. 7.45	250
		6,000	21. 7.45	1
		100	22. 7.45 to 31. 8.45	41
		Uncontrolled intake	1. 9.45 to 3.10.45	33
		20	4.10.45 to 3. 1.46	92
670	4. 1.46 to 15. 1.46	12		
Parry ..	10	10	18.12.44 to 26. 8.45	252

TABLE 30 (continued)

Name	Period on preliminary diet* (days)	Vitamin C supplement (mg. daily)	Period on supplement	
			Dates	No. of days
Proctor ..	42	10	13.11.44 to 8. 1.46	422
		560	9. 1.46 to 18. 1.46	10
Robinson ..	21	0	13.11.44 to 26. 7.45	256
		10	27. 7.45 to 18.11.45	115
		20	19.11.45 to 3. 1.46	46
		420	4. 1.46 to 16. 1.46	13
Sanderson ..	42	0	13.11.44 to 26. 7.45	256
		10	27. 7.45 to 18.11.45	115
		20	19.11.45 to 3. 1.46	46
		660	4. 1.46 to 15. 1.46	12
Tridgell ..	42	0	13.11.44 to 4. 8.45	265
		10	5. 8.45 to 8. 1.46	157
		620	9. 1.46 to 20. 1.46	12
Way	11	10	18.12.44 to 27. 5.45	161
		0	28. 5.45 to 4. 6.45	8
		10	5. 6.45 to 1. 7.45	27
		0	2. 7.45 to 7. 8.45	37
		5	8. 8.45 to 10.12.45	125
		670	11.12.45 to 20.12.45	10
Whinfield ..	20	0	11.12.44 to 17.12.44	7
		10	18.12.44 to 27. 5.45	161
		0	28. 5.45 to 7. 8.45	71
		5	8. 8.45 to 10.12.45	125
		670	11.12.45 to 19.12.45	10
Williams, D.	42	0	13.11.44 to 16. 5.45	185
		500	17. 5.45 to ?	?
Williams, H.	42	0	13.11.44 to 4. 6.45	204
		20	5. 6.45 to 26. 7.45	52
Wodeman ..	42	0	13.11.44 to 24. 6.45	224
		10	25. 6.45 to 3.10.45	101
		20	4.10.45 to 3. 1.46	92
		830	4. 1.46 to 17. 1.46	14
Woodhouse ..	42	10	13.11.44 to 8. 1.46	422
		640	9. 1.46 to 18. 1.46	10
Another ..	42	0	13.11.44 to 6. 8.45	267

* A mixed diet containing about 50 to 70 mg. vitamin C daily, natural or synthetic.

TABLE 44

Number and duration of colds as recorded by certain of the volunteers in their own notebooks

Name	Vitamin C (mg. daily)	Date	Number of days	Number of colds	Remarks
<i>Bartley</i> ..	70	9. 1.45	2	1	
		11. 3.45	2	1	
		18. 5.45	5	1	
		27. 9.45	4	1	
		11.10.45	1	1	
		13.12.45	6	1	
		Total	20	6	
<i>Garling</i> ..	70	7. 1.45	15	1	
		26. 2.45	5	1	
		7. 5.45	3	1	
		Total	23	3	
<i>Hill</i> ..	70	12.11.44	1	1	
		13. 1.45	6	1	
		29. 6.45	1	1	
		22. 8.45	1	1	
		29.12.45	7	1	
		Total	16	5	
<i>Golding</i> ..	10	5.12.44	14	1	
		28.12.44	13	1	
		23. 2.45	8	1	
		1. 5.45	11	1	
		1. 6.45	1	1	
		23. 6.45	11	1	
		20.10.45	7	1	
		28.11.45	6	1	
		Total	71	8	
<i>Jackson</i> ..	10	11. 1.45	1	1	
		5. 3.45	1	1	
		1.11.45	3	1	
		10.11.45	7	1	
		Total	12	4	
<i>Way</i> ..	10	3. 1.46	4	1	
		Total	4	1	
<i>Woodhouse</i>	10	23.11.44	3	1	
		29.12.44	1	1	
		9. 4.45	1	1	
		2. 6.45	5	1	
		17. 8.45	1	1	
		Total	11	5	

TABLE 44 (continued)

Name	Vitamin C (mg. daily)	Date	Number of days	Number of colds	Remarks
<i>Drake</i> ..	0	8.12.44	2	1	Dosed 3.7.45
		27.12.44	16	1	
		Total	18	2	
<i>Hudson</i> ..	0	7.12.44	16	1	Dosed 30.7.45
		21. 3.45	9	1	
		14. 7.45	11	1	
		2.10.45	13	1	
		11.11.45	16	1	
		9. 1.46	9	1	
		Total	74	6	
<i>Robinson</i> .	0	31.12.44	2	1	Dosed 27.7.45
		26. 6.45	3	1	
		26.10.45	1	1	
		Total	6	3	
<i>Sanderson</i>	0	21. 1.45	24	1	Dosed 27.7.45
		27. 4.45	17	1	
		18. 6.45	3	1	
		22. 9.45	7	1	
		Total	51	4	
<i>Tridgell</i> ..	0	13.11.44	8	1	Dosed 5.8.45
		28.12.44	4	1	
		15. 1.45	14	1	
		2. 4.45	15	1	
		27. 4.45	3	1	
		2. 5.45	9	1	
		29. 6.45	8	1	
		9. 8.45	1	1	
		22. 9.45	5	1	
		12.10.45	7	1	
		23.11.45	6	1	
		26.12.45	21	1	
		30. 1.46	5	1	
		Total	106	13	
<i>Wodeman</i>	0	23. 3.45	3	1	Dosed 25.6.45
		9. 1.46	3	1	
		Total	6	2	

Appendix 3: Data set based on Appendix 2.

This is the dataset used by Jowett. This is collected from data in Appendix 1. This is used in all analyses **A** to **E**.

```
> SheffieldJowett
      ID Dose Days Days_1 Deprived Cured
1  Bartley  70   2     0      0      1
2  Bartley  70   2     0      0      1
3  Bartley  70   5     0      0      1
4  Garling  70  15     0      0      1
5  Garling  70   5     0      0      1
6  Garling  70   3     0      0      1
7    Hill   70   1     1      0      1
8    Hill   70   6     0      0      1
9    Hill   70   1     1      0      1
10 Golding  10  14     0      0      1
11 Golding  10  13     0      0      1
12 Golding  10   8     0      0      1
13 Golding  10  11     0      0      1
14 Golding  10   1     1      0      1
15 Golding  10  11     0      0      1
16 Jackson  10   1     1      0      1
17 Jackson  10   1     1      0      1
18 Woodhouse 10   3     0      0      1
19 Woodhouse 10   1     1      0      1
20 Woodhouse 10   1     1      0      1
21 Woodhouse 10   5     0      0      1

22  Drake   0   2     0      1      1
23  Drake   0  16     0      1      1
24  Hudson   0  16     0      1      1
25  Hudson   0   9     0      1      1
26  Hudson   0  11     0      1      1
27 Robinson  0   2     0      1      1
28 Robinson  0   3     0      1      1
29 Sanderson  0  24     0      1      1
30 Sanderson  0  17     0      1      1
31 Sanderson  0   3     0      1      1
32 Tridgell  0   8     0      1      1
33 Tridgell  0   4     0      1      1
34 Tridgell  0  14     0      1      1
35 Tridgell  0  15     0      1      1
36 Tridgell  0   3     0      1      1
37 Tridgell  0   9     0      1      1
38 Tridgell  0   8     0      1      1
39 Wodeman   0   3     0      1      1
```

```
table(SheffieldJowett$Deprived)
```

```
0 1
21 18
```

```
> table(SheffieldJowett$Deprived, SheffieldJowett$Days)
```

```

  1 2 3 4 5 6 8 9 11 13 14 15 16 17 24
0 7 2 2 0 3 1 1 0 2 1 1 1 0 0 0
1 0 2 4 1 0 0 2 2 1 0 1 1 2 1 1
```

Appendix 4: Findings in the Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) trial [72; 4.1]

Variable	Placebo	Vitamin C	Difference	P ^{a)}
Participants	1100	335		
Vitamin C dose (mg/day)	10-15	50-300		
Common colds	286	72	-17%	0.047
Colds treated in the Sick Quarters	253	59	-23% ^{b)}	0.017
Days in hospital	6.4	6.32		
Tonsillitis ^{c)}	94	29	0%	
Admitted to hospital	83	18	-30% ^{b)}	0.086
Days in hospital, mean	16.7	10.1	-40%	0.0026
Days in hospital, SD	11.86	6.96		
Days in hospital per infected ^{d)}	14.7	6.3	-57%	0.0021 ^{d)}
Pneumonia	17	0	-100%	0.006
Rheumatic fever ^{e)}	16	0	-100%	0.007
Days spent in the sick room due to 'infective conditions' per boy, mean	4.98	2.5	-50%	<0.00001^{f)}

Data are from [72; 4.1].

^{a)} P(1-tail) is shown. For the 2×2 tables, the mid-P is calculated. See Appendix 5 in this supplement.

^{b)} Difference and P-value calculated from the population of all participants.

^{c)} Authors stated: “The term ‘tonsillitis’ is used here to be an index of haemolytic streptococcal disease of the nose and throat, and covers all such terms as ‘tonsillitis’, ‘sore throat’, ‘otitis media’, ‘pharyngitis’ and ‘cervical adenitis’, as nearly all these cases are of haemolytic streptococcal origin. Throat swabs were taken of large numbers of cases of tonsillitis to determine that the haemolytic streptococcus was the causative organism” (p 12).

^{d)} Days in hospital per infected schoolboy.

In the placebo group: $83 \times 16.7 / 94 = 14.7$ days.

In the vitamin C group: $18 \times 10.1 / 29 = 6.3$ days.

Combination of the tonsillitis P-values using Fisher’s method:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fisher%27s_method

```
> (1- pchisq(-2*(log(0.086) + log(0.0026)), 4))
[1] 0.0021
```

^{e)} Glazebrook and Thomson do not specify the criteria they used to diagnose rheumatic fever. See the comments below for more details.

^{f)} The SD values were not reported for “days spent in the sick room”. In most vitamin C common cold trials the SD for the duration has been on average 70% of the mean duration of colds [4.2]. Here I use a conservative imputation of SD being 100% of the mean duration, see below for the calculation.

Calculating the P-value for “Days in hospital due to tonsillitis” and “Days spent in the sick room”, using the Ratio of Means approach, see Appendix 4.

	Study	Ne	Me	Se	Nc	Mc	Sc	ROM	LnROM	SDe	SDc	SElnROM	z	p
1	Friedrich (test)	9	213.0	67.0	10	177	40	1.2	0.19	0.011	0.00511	0.127	1.5	9.3e-01
2	Glazebrook SickTonsillitis	18	10.1	7.0	83	17	12	0.6	-0.50	0.026	0.00608	0.180	-2.8	2.6e-03
3	Glazebrook SickRoom	335	2.5	2.5	1100	5	5	0.5	-0.69	0.003	0.00091	0.062	-11.0	1.2e-28

```
> riskratio.small(GTColds)
```

```
$data
```

```
Outcome
Predictor Disease1 Disease2 Total
Exposed1      814      286 1100
Exposed2      263       72  335
Total         1077      358 1435
```

```
$p.value
```

```
two-sided
Predictor midp.exact fisher.exact chi.square
Exposed2  0.093467    0.097693    0.095063
```

```
> (P_1tail=0.09347/2)
```

```
[1] 0.0467
```

```
> riskratio.small(GTColdsSick)
```

```
$data
```

```
Outcome
Predictor Disease1 Disease2 Total
Exposed1      847      253 1100
Exposed2      276       59  335
Total         1123      312 1435
```

```
$measure
```

```
risk ratio with 95% C.I.
Predictor estimate lower upper
Exposed2  0.76342 0.59123 0.98575
```

```
$p.value
```

```
two-sided
Predictor midp.exact fisher.exact chi.square
Exposed2  0.03436    0.040917    0.036332
```

```
> (P_1tail=0.03436/2)
```

```
[1] 0.0171
```

```
> riskratio.small(GTpneumonia)
```

```
$data
```

```
Outcome
Predictor Disease1 Disease2 Total
Exposed1      1083      17 1100
Exposed2      335       0  335
Total         1418      17 1435
```

```
$p.value
```

```
two-sided
Predictor midp.exact fisher.exact chi.square
Exposed2  0.010581    0.017995    0.022082
```

```
> (P_1tail=0.01058/2)
```

```
[1] 0.00529
```

```
> riskratio.small(GTrheumfever)
```

```
$data
```

```
Outcome
Predictor Disease1 Disease2 Total
Exposed1      1084      16 1100
Exposed2      335       0  335
Total         1419      16 1435
```

```
$p.value
```

```
two-sided
Predictor midp.exact fisher.exact chi.square
Exposed2  0.013852    0.031415    0.02643
```

```
> (P_1tail=0.01385/2)
```

```
[1] 0.00692
```

Allocation to treatment groups

In the Glazebrook and Thomson trial [4.1], allocation to treatment groups was carried out by institute ‘divisions’ and not on the basis of individual boys. Therefore, in the Cochrane review on vitamin C and pneumonia (2013) the trial was also analysed using the ‘division’ as the unit of observation [4.3].

Distribution of pneumonia cases in the five control divisions was 5, 3, 2, 4 and 3 (mean 3.40 cases per division) and in the two vitamin C divisions it was 0 and 0. Assuming that the mean of the control divisions was a suitable estimate for the Poisson distribution mean provided basis for the statistical analysis.

The size of the individual divisions was not stated in the paper but the two vitamin C divisions had on average 167 boys ($335/2$) and the five control divisions 220 boys ($1100/5$), thus the size of the vitamin C divisions was 0.761 times the size of the control divisions. The mean incidence was adjusted by this ratio, such that we expected 2.59 pneumonia cases per vitamin C division, assuming the same average incidence as for the control divisions. With this Poisson mean, the probability that there were no cases of pneumonia in two separate vitamin C divisions was calculated as having a P-value of 0.0056. Accordingly, using a ‘division’ as the unit of observation does not change the conclusions.

```
> (Control <- mean(c(5,3,2,4,3)))  
[1] 3.4  
> (RatioBoys <- (335/2)/(1100/5))  
[1] 0.761  
> (lambda <- Control*RatioBoys)  
[1] 2.59  
> dpois(0, lambda)^2  
[1] 0.0056
```

Diagnosis of rheumatic fever

Glazebrook and Thomson noted regarding pneumonia and rheumatic fever that “These cases were subjected to special investigations by us (X-rays, etc.) to establish certain criteria for the diagnosis”.

While the diagnosis of pneumonia in the late 1930s appears consistent with the modern understanding of the condition, the same cannot confidently be said for rheumatic fever. The Jones criteria, which currently guide the diagnosis of rheumatic fever, were not published until 1944 [4.4,4.5]. Although rheumatic fever typically presents with painful joints and carditis, these symptoms also occur in vitamin C deficiency. Notably, Glazebrook and Thomson observed reduced morbidity from streptococcal infections – the primary cause of rheumatic fever – raising the possibility that vitamin C might have influenced its occurrence. However, due to the lack of diagnostic details, it remains unclear how closely the reported rheumatic fever cases align with today’s definition of rheumatic fever. Despite this uncertainty, the reported difference between the low-dose (10-15 mg/day) and high-dose vitamin C groups remains valid, although the exact nature of the outcome is not well defined in this case.

Methods of the Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) trial are described in the report [4.1]. The structure of the paper is quite different from modern trial reports. Extracted here are the main descriptions:

In a large training school under our observation there were some 1500 youths aged 15-20 years. For the most part they were drawn from the lower wage-earning classes, and a large proportion came from Scotland and the North Midlands, where economic conditions are probably below the average for the country. It is a reasonable assumption that the previous dietary of the recruits had been somewhat deficient in vitamin C judged by the standards already quoted (p.4).

The food distribution [at the school] was badly managed. Electric ovens were used to reheat the food, and to keep it hot whilst awaiting distribution. Often 8 hr. elapsed between the time the food was cooked and its arrival on the dining tables. The minimum time that heat was applied to the food, including the original cooking and the subsequent reheating, was 2 hr (p.4).

The total intake of vitamin C varied from about 10 to 15 mg per student per day (p.5).

The calcium and vitamin B content of the dietary of the institution could perhaps be criticized, but the only outstanding deficiency, according to modern standards, was in vitamin C. As far as this one factor was concerned, the boys were almost certainly worse off, subsisting on the institution diet, than they would have been at home (p.17).

Pure ascorbic acid powder was added to... the morning cocoa, and an evening glass of milk. The mixing was done in bulk in the kitchens before issue. The powder dissolved quickly and easily, and did not alter the appearance or taste of the vehicle (p.7).

Thus, the trial corresponds functionally to a placebo-controlled trial because the participants were unable to identify the treatment, although no inactive powder was added to the cocoa and milk of the control group.

The establishment was divided into seven groups or divisions for administrative purposes. The youths of one division worked as a unit, and occupied certain tables in the dining hall. To some extent each division occupied particular dormitories but this separation was not absolute, and there was a fair amount of mixing of divisions in the sleeping quarters. Sleeping and feeding conditions were, of course, the same for all divisions (p.12).

Careful records had been kept of the incidence of all infections for 1½ years before the observations described here were begun. In the preceding year there had been an epidemic of tonsillitis, which had affected all the divisions uniformly, so that they could not be regarded as separate units within the larger populations (p.12).

The above suggests that exposure to infectious agents was reasonably uniform over the study population.

The observations were made by supplying vitamin C in the form of pure ascorbic acid to one or more divisions. This was considered to be the only practical method of carrying out the observations without introducing unnecessary complications. For example, it was not possible to choose boys at random as it would have been impossible to supply them with vitamin C-treated cocoa or milk in the dining room. With the method actually chosen, all that was necessary was to add vitamin C to the supplies of cocoa or milk serving the tables for the appropriate divisions (p.12).

Moreover, all of the divisions had a population more or less the same as regards duration of stay in the establishment ('institution age'). Infectious diseases were more common amongst those who had more recently joined the institution (p.12).

When a youth fell ill he was admitted to Sick Quarters unless his complaint was very mild. In the latter case he was placed on the out-patients list and excused all duties except attendance at school instruction. Most of the cases of common cold and tonsillitis were admitted to Sick Quarters. In analysing the durations of illnesses, observations were restricted to the cases in the Sick Quarters. The number of days spent there was obviously a more reliable index of the duration of illness, since the

patient was under constant medical supervision. Frequently when a youth was discharged from the Sick Quarters he was put on the out-patients list, and this 'convalescent period' was neglected. The admission to and discharge from the hospital was not under our control (p.13).

The diet in the Sick Quarters was basically similar to that of the healthy boys. It was modified, of course, to suit the needs of the sick, but was prepared in the central kitchens and suffered an equally drastic loss of its vitamin C. When a student from the experimental division fell ill and was admitted to Sick Quarters, his dosage of ascorbic acid was continued there (p.14).

The period of treatment of cases of tonsillitis and common cold in the Sick Quarters was completely outside our control, and no biased attitudes influenced these durations from which we have drawn our conclusions (p.16).

[pneumonia... rheumatic fever] ... These cases were-subjected to special investigations by us (X-rays, etc.) to establish certain criteria for the diagnosis. There was, however, in our opinion a relationship between these conditions (p.16).

It was not stated whether the diagnosis of pneumonia was carried out by the trial authors of the paper or by the physicians at the Sick Quarters. Although the method of diagnosing pneumonia was not described in detail in the paper, with the given descriptions and the severe pathological processes occurring in pneumonia it seems unlikely that administration of vitamin C in cocoa and milk could have led to detection bias.

References

4.1. Glazebrook AJ, Thomson S. The administration of vitamin C in a large institution and its effect on general health and resistance to infection. *J Hyg (Lond)*. 1942;42:1-19.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0022172400012596>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2199803>

Related papers:

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2239225> [Description of the trial]

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2162337>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2164503>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2164703>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2210931>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2286225>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609923>

Linus Pauling's analyses of the Glazebrook (1942) trial:

<https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/coll/pauling/rnb/31/31-103.html>

<https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/coll/pauling/rnb/33/33-034.html>

<https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/coll/pauling/rnb/33/33-035.html>

4.2. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C for preventing and treating the common cold.

Cochrane Database Syst Rev. 2013;2013:CD000980.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8078152>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225864>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/273209193>

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd000980.pub4>

4.3. Hemilä H, Louhiala P. Vitamin C for preventing and treating pneumonia.

Cochrane Database Syst Rev. 2013;(8):CD005532.

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225862>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/6549713>

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd005532.pub3>

4.4. Jones TD. The diagnosis of rheumatic fever. *JAMA*. 1944;126(8):481-484.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1944.02850430015005>

4.5. Gewitz MH, et al. Revision of the Jones Criteria for the diagnosis of acute rheumatic fever in the era of Doppler echocardiography. *Circulation*. 2015;131(20):1806-1818.

<https://doi.org/10.1161/cir.0000000000000205>

Appendix 5. Statistical issues.

1-tailed P

P(1-tail)-values are shown in this paper, since the main question is whether higher levels of vitamin C decrease the incidence or duration of the respiratory infections or not, and this question is unidirectional. If the P(1-tail) is greater than about 0.97, then there is a reason to assume harm in the treatment group of the particular trial. For $P(1\text{-tail}) < 0.5$, the P(2-tail) is twice the P(1-tail) and easy to calculate if the reader prefers the 2-tailed values.

Relative scale: Ratio of Means (RoM)

It has been shown that the relative scale much better captures the effect of treatments on many continuous outcomes such as the duration of colds [5.1-5.5]. The ratio of means is a useful scale to compare 2 groups [5.1]. Friedrich et al. give the formula for calculating the RoM estimate and its 95% CI [5.1].

For example, if the mean length of colds as calculated by Jowett (1953)
of non-deprived subjects = 3.3 days
of colds of deprived subjects = 6.4 days

We can calculate that on average colds were longer by 3.1 days in deprived subjects ($6.4 - 3.3 = 3.1$). We can also calculate that colds were 94% longer in deprived subjects ($6.4/3.3 = 1.94 = \text{RoM}$). The relative scale estimate is more consistent in the analysis of duration data [4.2-4.5].

5.1. Friedrich JO, Adhikari NK, Beyene J. Ratio of means for analyzing continuous outcomes in meta-analysis performed as well as mean difference methods. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2011;64:556–64.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2010.09.016>

5.2. Hemilä H. Many continuous variables such as the duration of the common cold should be analyzed using the relative scale. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2016;78:128-9.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2016.03.020>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/173096>

5.3. Hemilä H. Duration of the common cold and similar continuous outcomes should be analyzed on the relative scale: a case study of two zinc lozenge trials. *BMC Med Res Methodol.* 2017;17(1):82.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-017-0356-y>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5427521>

5.4. Hemilä H, Chalker E, Tukiainen J. Quantile treatment effect of zinc lozenges on common cold duration: a novel approach to analyze the effect of treatment on illness duration. *Front Pharmacol.* 2022;13:817522.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.817522>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8844493>

5.5. Hemilä H, Pirinen M. Estimating quantile treatment effect on the original scale of the outcome variable: a case study of common cold treatments. *Trials.* 2025;26:541.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-025-09265-z>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC12645726>

mid-P

In 2×2 tables, when there are only a few cases in one group, the mid-P value is the most appropriate method to calculate the P values for the differences in the treatment groups [5.6-5.9]. Table 7 from [5.6] illustrates the rationalization; see below.

5.6. Hemilä H. *Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections?*

University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland 2006: p.21 (Table 7) [see below].

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6395595>

5.7. Lancaster HO. Significance tests in discrete distributions. *J Am Stat Assoc.* 1961;56:223-34.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/2282247>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/2282247>

5.8. Berry G, Armitage P. Mid-P confidence intervals. *Statistician.* 1995;44:417-23.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/2348891>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/2348891>

5.9. Lydersen S, Fagerland MW, Laake P. Recommended tests for association in 2 x 2 tables.

Stat Med. 2009;28(7):1159–75.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.3531>

Table 7. Rationalization of the mid-P-value

Let us assume that we observe results forming the following 2x2 table:

1	1
1	1

In the Fisher exact test, we calculate the probability of all tables that have the same fixed margins (3 tables in this case):

		Probability of the table:
2	0	P[up] = 1/6
0	2	
1	1	P[obs] = 4/6
1	1	
0	2	
2	0	P[low] = 1/6

The lower 1-tailed ‘Fisher P’ adds the probabilities of the observed table (P[obs]) and the probabilities of the tables of the lower tail.

Thus here,

$$\text{Fisher } P[1-t] = 4/6 + 1/6 = 5/6 = 0.833.$$

The lower 1-tailed ‘mid-P’ adds half of the probability of the observed table ($\frac{1}{2} \times P[\text{obs}]$) and the probabilities of the tables of the lower tail.

Thus here,

$$\text{mid-P}[1-t] = 2/6 + 1/6 = 3/6 = 0.5.$$

With the ‘observed table’ having 1 observation in each cell, there is no evidence of any difference from the null effect, and we should expect the corresponding P[1-t] to be exactly 0.5. In this respect the mid-P corresponds to scaling the P-value so that P[1-t] = 0.5 corresponds to the null effect. Thus the mid-P modification is consistent with the t-test, which also yields P[1-t] = 0.5 if there is no difference between the groups, so that their means are equal.

The 1-tailed mid-P-values never add up to a 2-tailed mid-P-value above 1. In contrast, the 1-tailed Fisher P-values may add up to the 2-tailed Fisher P-value above 1 as in the case above (Fisher P[2-t] = 2 x 0.833 = 1.67); however, P values above 1 are inconsistent with the concept of probability.

Appendix 6. Replication of the Jowett (1953) analysis.

```
> SheffieldJowett$logDays <- 20*log10(SheffieldJowett$Days)
> 10^(with(SheffieldJowett, tapply(logDays, Deprived, mean))/20)
      0      1
3.287 6.998
```

Jowett calculated:

vitamin C administered	vitamin C deprived
3.3	6.4

There are differences in the mean duration of colds in the deprived groups in this calculation and in Jowett's calculation. They are probably explained by rounding due to the use of pencil and paper in the 1940s.

The quantile-quantile plot shows that short (1-day) and long colds substantially deviate from the normal distribution even after the $-20 \times \log_{10}$ transformation used by Jowett.

Total sum of squares in Jowett table; see Table 18 at the bottom of this page.

```
> #Jowett sum of squares
> (431.8 + 1092.1 + 1365.8)
[1] 2889.7
```

With no explanatory variables, the total sum of squares is close to Jowett’s sum:

```
> SheffAOV_0
Call:
  aov(formula = logDays ~ 1, data = SheffieldJowett)

Terms:
              Residuals
Sum of Squares  2887.59
Deg. of Freedom    38
```

Including vitamin C deprivation and ID:

```
> SheffAOV
Call:
  aov(formula = logDays ~ Deprived + ID, data = SheffieldJowett)

Terms:
      Deprived      ID Residuals
Sum of Squares  417.50 1103.78  1366.31
Deg. of Freedom    1      10      27

Residual standard error: 7.11366
1 out of 13 effects not estimable
Estimated effects may be unbalanced
> summary(SheffAOV)
      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
Deprived  1    417    417      8.25 0.0078
ID       10   1104    110      2.18 0.0523
Residuals 27   1366     51
```

TABLE 18

Analysis of variance of transformed lengths of colds

Source of variation	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean square
Difference between groups	431.8	1	431.8 (1)
Differences between individuals within a group ..	1092.1	10	109.2 (2)
Variation of length of cold within an individual ..	1365.8	27	50.6 (3)

Appendix 7. Relative effect.

```
> Treatment = subset(SheffieldJowett, Deprived == 1)$Days
> table(Treatment)
Treatment
 2  3  4  8  9 11 14 15 16 17 24
 2  4  1  2  2  1  1  1  2  1  1

> Control = subset(SheffieldJowett, Deprived == 0)$Days
> table(Control)
Control
 1  2  3  5  6  8 11 13 14 15
 7  2  2  3  1  1  2  1  1  1

>
> (length(Treatment))
[1] 18
> (length(Control))
[1] 21
>
> (mean(Treatment))
[1] 9.278
> (mean(Control))
[1] 5.238
>
> (sd(Treatment))
[1] 6.506
> (sd(Control))
[1] 4.816
```

```
> ROM
      Study  Ne      Me      Se      Nc      Mc      Sc  LnROM      SDe      SDc  SElnROM      z
1  Friedrich (test)  9 213.00 67.00  10 177.00 40.00  0.185 0.01099 0.005  0.126  1.46
2      Sheffield  18  9.28  6.51  21  5.24  4.82  0.572 0.02732 0.040  0.259  2.20

      p  CIlo  CIhi  ROM
1 0.0723 0.938 1.543 1.203
2 0.0139 1.064 2.948 1.771
```

Appendix 8. Cox regression.

```
> SheffieldSurv <- Surv(SheffieldJowett$Days, SheffieldJowett$Cured)
> SheffieldSurv
 [1]  2  2  5 15  5  3  1  6  1 14 13  8 11  1 11  1  1  3
[19]  1  1  5  2 16 16  9 11  2  3 24 17  3  8  4 14 15  3
[37]  9  8  3
>
>
> Sheffield_Cox <- coxph(SheffieldSurv ~ SheffieldJowett$Deprived, ties="exact")
> Sheffield_Cox
Call:
coxph(formula = SheffieldSurv ~ SheffieldJowett$Deprived, ties = "exact")

              coef exp(coef) se(coef)      z
SheffieldJowett$Deprived -0.904      0.405    0.382 -2.37
                p
SheffieldJowett$Deprived 0.018

Likelihood ratio test=5.8 on 1 df, p=0.0161
n= 39, number of events= 39
>
> exp(confint(Sheffield_Cox))
                2.5 %    97.5 %
SheffieldJowett$Deprived 0.191611 0.855782
> (P = 0.0161/2)
[1] 0.00805
```

Appendix 9. QTE analysis.

Fig. 2 was calculated with the *bqte* program [22-23].

A. Using the vitamin C administration (10-70 mg/day) as the control on the x-axis.

```
Treatment = subset(SheffieldJowett, Deprived == 1)$Days
> table(Treatment)

Treatment
 2  3  4  8  9 11 14 15 16 17 24
 2  4  1  2  2  1  1  1  2  1  1

> Control = subset(SheffieldJowett, Deprived == 0)$Days
> table(Control)

Control
 1  2  3  5  6  8 11 13 14 15
 7  2  2  3  1  1  2  1  1  1

> res.bqte = bqte(Treatment = Treatment, Control = Control, tails = TRUE, at =
c(1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8)) #Estimate BQTE
Running bqte() with the following parameters.
length(Treatment): 18
length(Control): 21
K: 21
B: 2000
bqte.conf: 0.95
at: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8
bagging: TRUE
tails: TRUE
If you choose to change 'at' values, a recommended interval is [1, 8.71].
>
> #Check output of bqte() function
>

> res.bqte
  at bqte bqte.low bqte.up
1  1  2.23  1.000  5.42
2  2  3.96  0.818 10.47
```

at = 1 gives the estimate and 95% CI (low, up) for the effect on the control group 1-day colds.

at = 2 gives the estimate and 95% CI (low, up) for the effect on the control group 2-day colds.

Thus, according to this estimation, an 1-day cold in participants administered vitamin C (10-70 mg/day) becomes 2.23 days longer when a corresponding participant is deprived of vitamin C, leading to a colds of 3.23 days.

B. Using the vitamin C deprivation as the control on the x-axis.

```
> Treatment = subset(SheffieldJowett, Deprived == 0)$Days
> table(Treatment)

Treatment
 1  2  3  5  6  8 11 13 14 15
 7  2  2  3  1  1  2  1  1  1

> Control = subset(SheffieldJowett, Deprived == 1)$Days
> table(Control)

Control
 2  3  4  8  9 11 14 15 16 17 24
 2  4  1  2  2  1  1  1  2  1  1

> set.seed(1) #Set random seed for reproducible results
> res.bqte = bqte(Treatment = Treatment, Control = Control, tails = TRUE)
#Estimate BQTE
Running bqte() with the following parameters.
length(Treatment): 21
length(Control): 18
K: 18
B: 2000
bqte.conf: 0.95
at: 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14
bagging: TRUE
tails: TRUE
If you choose to change 'at' values, a recommended interval is [3, 14.3].
>
> #Check output of bqte() function
>

> res.bqte
  at  bqte bqte.low bqte.up
1   3 -1.68   -2.00  0.2461
2   4 -1.92   -3.00  1.2656
```

Appendix 10. Vitamin C deficiency and pneumonia in Alfred Hess' monograph on scurvy [44]

Alfred Hess – a pediatrician in the USA – was the most important clinical investigator of vitamin C deficiency in the early 20th century. He wrote a monograph about scurvy, in which he stated in several parts that there is an increased risk of pneumonia in scorbutic animals and humans. These statements are extracted below with their contexts; bold added.

Hess AF. Scurvy: Past and Present. Philadelphia PA: Lippincott USA; 1920.

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>

<https://digital.library.cornell.edu/catalog/chla2903792>

<https://archive.org/search?query=creator%3A%22Hess+Alfred%22+scurvy>

More relevant parts of Hess' book are extracted in:

Hemilä H. *The symptoms of vitamin C deficiency.*

1. *Observations and descriptions by Hess, Lind, Trotter and Blane.* Zenodo. 2024.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194>

p.88 [Chapter IV, Pathology of scurvy]

Lungs.—... Edema of the lungs is not uncommon, as we should expect, especially as a terminal condition. **Pneumonia**, lobular or lobar, is one of the most frequent complications and causes of death. Active tuberculosis is a not uncommon secondary manifestation.

p.99 [Chapter IV, Microscopic pathology of scurvy]

Lungs.—Hemorrhages of various size occur in the tissue of the lung or in the air spaces. Hemorrhagic infarcts also have been described, and Sato and Nambu report hyaline degeneration of the blood-vessel walls. Secondary **pneumonias**, usually broncho-pneumonic in type, are of common occurrence, and in many epidemics constitute the prevailing cause of death. Tuberculous lesions are also frequently present, and are stated to assume fresh activity as the result of the nutritional disorder. Edema occurs frequently, the fluid in the acini often containing red blood-cells. Subpleural hemorrhages, thickening of the pleura, purulent or fibrinous pleurisy are common lesions.

p.123 [Chapter V, Experimental scurvy; Guinea pigs]

On opening the chest, slight hemorrhages may be noted in the pericardium and in the visceral and costal pleuræ. The heart is frequently enlarged, and the pericardial sac contains an excess of serum; the right ventricle, however, is not found disproportionately hypertrophied. **Pneumonia** is met with very frequently and constitutes a common terminal infection.

p.179 [Chapter VII, Symptomatology and diagnosis of scurvy]

Nowadays, the disease usually does not reach this stage, and rarely progresses further. If, however, the patient remains untreated, he becomes progressively weaker and more lethargic; there is frequent palpitation, shortness of breath, and increasing loss of weight. The pains in the limbs render him helpless and an object of pity. Marked edema may be added to the picture as the result of starvation, so that the legs become swollen, and even the face becomes bloated. Hemorrhages into the skin as large as the palm of the hand appear on different parts of the body. The gums swell to such an extent that they overlap and may even hide the teeth and protrude from the mouth as foul fungoid growth. Death comes about in various ways. Frequently sudden and fatal syncope occurs, due to heart weakness or to the pouring out of fluid into the pleural or the pericardial cavities. Another frequent cause of death is secondary infection, resulting in **pneumonia**, which finally ends the suffering of the patient. The fatal outcome is thus described in the narrative of Lord Anson's voyage...

p.182 [Chapter VII, Symptomatology and diagnosis of scurvy]

Pericarditis, hydrothorax, pleurisy with effusion, **pneumonia**, are common complications of severe forms of scurvy. **Lind reports** that the dominant complication varies in different epidemics; that on one cruise many cases of diarrhoea would occur and on another **many pulmonary infections**.

[see below James Lind's section to which Alfred Hess refers above]

p.202 [Chapter VII, Symptomatology and diagnosis of scurvy]

The main involvement of the respiratory system in scurvy is the polypnoea just described in connection with the cardiorespiratory syndrome. There is no aphonia, a sign so typical of adult and of infantile beriberi, although at times the voice is abnormal and whining. The lungs frequently show some dullness posteriorly, which may be due to engorgement or to the pressure of the enlarged heart. **Pneumonia** is a frequent complication and edema a terminal event. Hydrothorax associated with hydropericardium is of frequent occurrence, and was noted in the early description of this disease in adults and in the first account of Barlow. These effusions rarely progress to what may be termed the clinical degree and under antiscorbutic treatment are rapidly absorbed.

p.217 [Chapter VII, Symptomatology and diagnosis of scurvy]

We have already considered numerous *complications* of scurvy, and shall therefore not go over this ground again. Many of them are due to hemorrhages or to serous effusions in various parts of the body. Another large group in adults as well as in infants are the result of infection. **The respiratory tract is particularly susceptible, pneumonia** constituting the most common cause of death. In infants we meet with frequent attacks of "grippe," widespread occurrence of *nasal diphtheria*, furunculosis and torpid ulcers of the skin, pyelitis, otitis, adenitis, etc. We have encountered nasal diphtheria—with typical bloody mucous discharge—so frequently in connection with scurvy, that where this local infection occurs among a group of infants they should be carefully examined for latent or mild scurvy. Aschoff and Koch recently have laid emphasis on the frequency with which diphtheria complicated scurvy among adults (soldiers). Dysentery is another complication resulting from an invasion of bacteria. Local infections occur more often in adults than in infants—cervical adenitis following gingival pyorrhoea, "bubo" of the groin following infection of the lower extremity, abscess of the calf of the leg following hemorrhage into this region.

p.227 [Chapter VIII, Prognosis of scurvy]

In adults the heart may be weakened by scurvy, and death may result from cardiac failure. Cardiac disturbances occur also in infantile scurvy. This involvement might be expected, in view of the tachycardia (cardiorespiratory phenomenon) which is so frequent a symptom of infantile scurvy. The heart may be rapid for months or even for years after the disorder, and tachycardia may develop on the occasion of even a mild infectious disease. For example, a fever of 101°, due to a common coryza, may cause the heart-beat to rise to perhaps 180 a minute. Children so affected succumb readily to infection, especially to **pneumonia**, which may lead to sudden collapse followed by death.

An important factor in the prognosis of scurvy, as in that of other disorders due to a lack of vitamins, is the marked susceptibility to infection. **Even latent or subacute scurvy causes a peculiar susceptibility to diphtheria** (especially the nasal type), to coryza, bronchitis, and **pneumonia**. A perusal of the literature shows that this susceptibility was noted by the older authors in relation to adults.

Later comments on vitamin C and infections by Hess in 1932:

Hess AF. Recent advances in knowledge of scurvy and the antiscorbutic vitamin.

JAMA. 1932;98(17):1429-33.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609694>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1932.02730430005002>

ASSOCIATION OF SCURVY WITH INFECTIONS

Another point that has been brought into prominence in connection with adult as well as infantile scurvy is its intimate association with the infectious process. In 1917 I stated that "one of the striking and important symptoms of scurvy is a susceptibility to infection (furunculosis, nasal diphtheria, grippe, etc.)." In this connection it may be mentioned that nasal diphtheria was noted among a group of scorbutic infants in spite of the fact that many of them gave a negative Schick reaction. Findlay, attacking the problem from an experimental standpoint, showed that guinea-pigs which suffered from chronic scurvy and showed but few clinical symptoms manifested a decreased resistance to bacterial infection; this he attributed to degenerative changes in the bone marrow. About this time Cramer and Kingsbury emphasized the importance of vitamin A in warding off infections, associating this susceptibility with a decrease in the number of platelets of the blood. Abels, in a monograph on scurvy, stressed this relationship of the scorbutic state to infection, giving the name "dysergie" to the nutritional disturbance which occasions the heightened susceptibility. Recently, Minot and his colleagues came to the conclusion that adult scurvy can be precipitated by infectious processes; in other words, that latent scurvy can by this means be changed to manifest scurvy. In general, therefore, investigations in the laboratory as well as clinical observations are in agreement in stressing the interrelationship of scurvy and bacterial infection.

The 1917 paper:

Hess AF. Infantile scurvy. Part V. A study of its pathogenesis.

Am J Dis Child. 1917;14:337-53.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609522>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/archpedi.1917.01910110018002>

Hess AF. Diet, nutrition and infection. *N Engl J Med.* 1932;207:637-48.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609616>

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM193210132071501>

In regard to *vitamin C*, I shall refer only to the bearing of this vitamin on infections, more particularly of the respiratory tract. In 1917, in a paper on the pathogenesis of infantile scurvy, I emphasized the fact that a lack of the antiscorbutic factor which leads to scurvy, at the same time predisposes to infections. This enhanced susceptibility has been confirmed by Abels, Ludwig Meyer and many others. It exists even before the scorbutic signs are manifest in the stage which is better termed "latent scurvy" than "Praeskorbutus" as the abnormal scorbutic state already exists. Similar susceptibility to infections goes hand in hand with adult scurvy. This was pointed out years ago by Lind and others in connection with scurvy in the mercantile marine and among the soldiers in times of war, for example, in our Civil War and in the Crimean War.

But I wish to emphasize quite another aspect of infection in connection with infantile scurvy. In 1917, and again in 1920, I called attention to the "widespread occurrence of nasal diphtheria in infantile scurvy", remarking that "we have encountered nasal diphtheria—with typical bloody mucus discharge—so frequently in connection with scurvy that where this local infection occurs among a group of infants they should be carefully examined for latent or mild scurvy". At the same time I drew attention to the fact that "clinical tests showed that the blood contains sufficient antitoxin (diphtheria) to afford protection." These were the days previous to the use of toxin-antitoxin. Much to our surprise, some of these cases gave a negative Schick test in spite of the definite clinical signs

of nasal diphtheria. In two instances the diphtheria bacilli were tested on guinea pigs and found to be virulent. Not long after these observations an infant died from diphtheria of the larynx which developed although the Schick test was negative. At postmortem a typical membrane was found on the larynx.

Since this time, there has been little opportunity to investigate this subject, as diphtheria has been banished from our institution by the routine use of toxin-antitoxin. Recently, however, we have met with three cases of nasal diphtheria which developed soon after their admission to the institution. These cases were characterized by the typical bloody nasal discharge. In two instances the cultures showed avirulent bacilli, in one which was obtained in December, 1930, the bacilli from the nose were virulent. In spite of this fact, not only was the Schick test negative, but tests carried out in February, 1931, with increasing doses of toxin 1/50-1/40-1/30-1/20-1/10-1/5 M.L.D. all failed to induce a skin reaction. As the result of these experiences we infer that a lack of the antiscorbutic vitamin exerts a local effect on the mucous membrane which diminishes its immunity, but at the same time may not be accompanied by a lowering of systemic immunity. It is probable that a similar phenomenon holds true in connection with a deficiency of vitamin A and that the marked changes in the epithelium, described by Wolbach, bring about a local diminution in resistance. Susceptibility to infections of the skin and of the respiratory tract which occur when this deficiency is marked may be largely a manifestation of a local pathological change.

James Lind and respiratory infections in vitamin C deficiency.

James Lind's treatise on scurvy is the most important text on the topic over the ages. However, at Lind's time there was no knowledge of bacteria and X-rays were not available, and for reasons such as these there was no concept of "pneumonia" in the same sense as was known at Hess' times and currently.

See links to several versions of Lind's treatise through:

Hemilä H. The symptoms of vitamin C deficiency.

1. Observations and descriptions by Hess, Lind, Trotter and Blane.

Zenodo. 2024.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194>

The full treatise is available:

<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107256644>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/bg2gxrzz> ed. 1753

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/hkvrjpk9> ed. 1757

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/xc2t7736> ed. 1757

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt> ed. 1772

<https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/009295546> ed. 1757

<https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/009295935> ed. 1772

<https://archive.org/search?query=creator%3A%22Lind+James%22+scurvy>

In our current context, the section below to which Hess referred may indicate that in 1747 there were respiratory viruses circulating on the ship, and because of the very low vitamin C levels, the sailors did not properly recover from the viral infections and some of them may have suffered from lower respiratory tract infections as a complication.

On the other hand, in 1746 there may have been viral gastroenteritis circulating so that scurvy exacerbated their symptoms.

This is the section to which Alfred Hess referred in his book on p. 182, see above.

Lind's text; bold added.

p.110-111 in Lind's 1st edition (Lind's 3rd edition p.105):

I observed a considerable difference in the genius of the disease in the two cruises ann. 1746 and 1747. **In the latter, when fevers from cold of the pleuritic and peripneumonic sort prevailed, it tended chiefly to affect the breast with a tightness, oppression, and a hard bound cough, by which a very viscid phlegm was with great difficulty brought up.** The fits of coughing were not constant, but extremely fatiguing ; and this was a universal complaint. Several at this season were feverish ; we had none in a salivation, and the fluxes were mild and manageable.

Whereas in the year 1746, when a different species of diseases prevailed, occasioned by the unwholesome newness of the ship's timbers, and diarrhœas were frequent, the scurvy proved more virulent and fatal. Its worst, most common, and troublesome symptoms, were salivations and dysenteries, especially the latter ; in which one Nichols died, and eight or ten more were landed at Plymouth in a very low and exhausted condition by it. I did not at that time remark any of them to be feverish, and **their breasts were but slightly affected.**

Appendix 11. Findings in the Cowan et al. (1942) trial [84; 11.1]

Variable	Placebo	Vitamin C	Difference	P
Participants	155	208		
Vitamin C dose (mg/day)	?	100-200		
Common colds per person, mean ^{a)}	1.9	2.2	-14%	0.0032
SD ^{a)}	1.00	1.01		
SE	0.08	0.07		
Percentage who had no colds	8.4%	11.5%	3.1 pp	
Days lost from school	1.6	1.1	-31%	0.0002
SD ^{b)}	1.6	1.1		

pp, percentage point

The data are from [84; 11.1].

^{a)} The authors reported the SE value, from which the SD is calculated.

The authors also reported difference between groups as “0.3 (SE 0.11)”, which gives the same P.

```
> (z <- 0.3/0.11)
[1] 2.7
> (p = pnorm(-z))
[1] 0.0032
```

^{b)} The authors did not report the SD value for “days lost from school”. The SD values were not reported. In most vitamin C common cold trials the SD for the duration has been on average 70% of the mean duration of colds [11.2]. Here I use a conservative imputation of SD being 100% of the mean duration. Calculation with the RoM approach gives:

	Study	Ne	Me	Se	Nc	MC	Sc	ROM	LnROM	SDe	SDC
1	Friedrich (test)	9	213.00	67.00	10	177.00	40.00	1.203	0.185	0.01099	0.005107
5	cowan	208	1.10	1.10	155	1.60	1.60	0.688	-0.375	0.00481	0.006452
	SElnROM										
1											
5											
	z										
1											
5											
	p										
1											
5											

Reduction in “days lost from school” was also reported in 1977 by Ludvigsson [11.3,11.4]

Cowan et al. wrote (1942) [11.1, p.1269]:

... The actual difference between the two groups [in the incidence of colds] during the year of the study amounts to one third of a cold per person. Statistical analysis of the data reveals that a difference as large as this would arise only three or four times in a hundred through chance alone. One may therefore consider this as probably a significant difference, and vitamin C supplement to the diet may therefore be judged to give a slight advantage in reducing the number of colds experienced.

11.1. Cowan DW, Diehl HS, Baker AB. Vitamins for the prevention of colds. *JAMA*. 1942;120(16):1268-71.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14674396>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1942.02830510006002>

Linus Pauling's analyses of the Cowan et al. (1942) trial:

<https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/coll/pauling/rnb/31/31-096.html>

<https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/coll/pauling/rnb/31/31-097.html>

<https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/coll/pauling/rnb/31/31-098.html>

<https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/coll/pauling/rnb/31/31-099.html>

<https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/coll/pauling/rnb/31/31-100.html>

<https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/coll/pauling/rnb/31/31-101.html>

<https://scarc.library.oregonstate.edu/coll/pauling/rnb/33/33-029.html>

The Cowan (1942) trial was included in Pauling's (1971) meta-analyses:

Pauling L. The significance of the evidence about ascorbic acid and the common cold.

Proc Natl Acad Sci USA. 1971;68:2678-81.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.68.11.2678>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC389499>

<https://profiles.nlm.nih.gov/101584639X101>

11.2. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C for preventing and treating the common cold.

Cochrane Database Syst Rev. 2013;2013:CD000980.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8078152>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225864>

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd000980.pub4>

<https://www.mv.helsinki.fi/home/hemila/CC> [Links to references]

11.3. Ludvigsson J, Hansson LO, Tibbling G. Vitamin C as a preventive medicine against common colds in children. *Scand J Infect Dis*. 1977;9(2):91-8.

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/22256528>

<https://doi.org/10.3109/inf.1977.9.issue-2.07>

11.4. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C reduces the severity of common colds: a meta-analysis.

BMC Public Health. 2023;23(1):2468.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-17229-8>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10712193>

Appendix 12. Benefit from vitamin C for common colds in UK trials after the Sheffield study.

Trial	Outcome	Effect	P
Charleston and Clegg 1972 [12.1,12.2]	Incidence of colds in males	-68%	0.00004
Elwood et al. 1976 [12.3,12.6]	Incidence of 'chest colds' in females	-18%	0.014
Tyrrell et al. 1977 [12.4,12.7]	Incidence of recurrent colds in males ^{a)}	-40%	0.018
Baird et al. 1979 [12.5,12.7]	Incidence of colds in males	-37%	0.00003

^{a)} Tyrrell et al. (1977) administered "10 g of ascorbic acid taken during the first 2½ days on the symptoms of the common cold". The outcome here is the incidence of second colds for the male participants who were treated with vitamin C or placebo for the first cold.

These trials were included in a 1997 systematic review of UK trials [12.8].
The meta-analysis was commented on, and comments were responded to [12.9].

12.1. Charleston SS, Clegg KM. Ascorbic acid and the common cold. *Lancet*. 1972;1(7765):1401-2.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(72\)91143-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(72)91143-9)
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4113614>

12.2. Clegg KM. Studies associated with ascorbic acid. *Acta Vitaminol Enzymol*. 1974;28:101-2.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13946103>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4615590>

12.3. Elwood PC, Lee HP, St Leger AS, Baird M, Howard AN. A randomized controlled trial of vitamin C in the prevention and amelioration of the common cold. *Br J Prev Soc Med*. 1976;30:193-6.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC478963>
<https://doi.org/10.1136/jech.30.3.193>

12.4. Tyrrell DA, Craig JW, Meada TW, White T. A trial of ascorbic acid in the treatment of the common cold. *Br J Prev Soc Med*. 1977;31:189-91.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC479021>
<https://doi.org/10.1136/jech.31.3.189>

12.5. Baird IM, Hughes RE, Wilson HK, Davies JE, Howard AN. The effects of ascorbic acid and flavonoids on the occurrence of symptoms normally associated with the common cold. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 1979;32:1686-90.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/32.8.1686>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/463806>

12.6. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C for the common cold and pneumonia. *Pol Arch Intern Med*. 2025;135(1):16926.
<https://doi.org/10.20452/pamw.16926>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/39803741>

12.7. Hemilä H. Vitamin C and sex differences in respiratory tract infections. *Respir Med*. 2008;102:625-626.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rmed.2007.12.011>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228090>

12.8. Hemilä H. Vitamin C intake and susceptibility to the common cold. *Br J Nutr*. 1997;77:59-72.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/223362>
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0007114500002889>

12.9. Bates CJ, Schorah CJ, Hemilä H. Vitamin C intake and susceptibility to the common cold: Invited commentaries and response. *Br J Nutr*. 1997;78:857-66.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/223364>
<https://doi.org/10.1079/BJN19970201>

Appendix 13. Possible socio-political roots for the bias against vitamin C supplements.

Rima Apple reviewed the history of vitamins in the USA in the 20th century and described a number of interesting patterns in the discussions about vitamins [13.1,13.2]. She did not take a particular stand on the question of whether vitamins are useful, harmful, or neutral, but instead analyzed the political views and discussions on the topic.

According to Apple, the concern about America's nutrition was not a concept generated by pharmaceutical companies pushing vitamin supplements. By the late 1930s, several studies documented the nation's poor diet, including eating vitamin poor foods, modern processing destroying parts of vitamins, and poor diets due to the Great Depression. These issues were well reported in the popular press in the early part of the previous century, and this context led to the origin of the vitamin industry. Thus, while many of the more recent advertisements are exaggerated and mislead consumers, the concern about nutrition among lay people originated from scientific findings that were reported in the popular press. Apple also described that many researchers found that workers receiving vitamins had considerably lower rates of absenteeism, stayed in their jobs longer, and even scored higher on their merit ratings [13.1, pp.3–10].

Apple described that there was a negative view by the American Medical Association (AMA) against vitamins tracing to the early 1900s. In her history of vitamins in the USA, she described that *“the American Medical Association (AMA) was most critical of the emerging [vitamin] industry. In articles and in editorials, starting as early as 1922, the organization called the commercial hype surrounding vitamins ‘a gigantic fraud’”* [13.1, p. 8]. Over and over again, the AMA campaigned against vitamin supplements, insisting that a diet lacking in vitamins would give rise to gross vitamin-deficiency diseases, and that these conditions were the concern of the doctor. According to AMA articles, vitamin pills were within the purview of the physician, not the layperson.

In Apple's view, commercial vitamin pills undercut the authority of medical practitioners over patients' health. Thus, concerns about power structure in respect to the new substances and who oversees the health of the population may have been one of the causes for the bias against vitamins. According to Apple, leaders of the AMA frequently worked with representatives of the FDA to denounce vitamin therapy as 'fraud'. They cautioned that little evidence existed to document the power of vitamins, except in clear cases of vitamin deficiency. Physicians dismissed the idea that vitamin supplementation could benefit the cold sufferer.

To my knowledge there is no comparable analysis of attitudes towards vitamins in the UK. However, it seems plausible that the focus was similarly on gross vitamin deficiencies; in the case of vitamin C on gums and wound healing.

Another informative analysis of the attitudes of mainstream medicine towards vitamins was by Goodwin and Tangum [13.2,13.3]. They also did not take a stand on the question of whether vitamins were useful or not, but analyzed the biases in US mainstream medicine, noting that it is not proof of bias to be concerned about toxicity or to be skeptical of claims of efficacy. Bias occurs when concern and skepticism are applied selectively to different but comparable topics.

They gave several examples to support their conclusions [13.3, p.2187].

Our thesis is that throughout much of the 20th century, American academic medicine was resistant to the concept that micronutrient supplementation might prove beneficial... This resistance is evident in several ways: (1) by uncritical acceptance of bad news about micronutrient supplements; reports of toxic effects were rarely questioned and widely quoted; (2) by the scornful, dismissive tone of the discussions about micronutrient supplementation in

textbooks of medicine, a tone avoided in most medical controversies; and (3) by the skeptical reaction greeting any claim of efficacy of a micronutrient, relative to other therapies; indeed, most claims were simply ignored.

Goodwin and Tangum reported that, over the preceding decades, there had been many areas of medical practice about which uncertainty and controversy existed, but in none of these discussions did one encounter the contemptuous descriptions found in the discussions of multiple vitamins.

Goodwin and Tangum also pointed out that there are many factors that influence the adoption of new medical treatments, including efficacy, toxic effects, and cost, but they also referred to financial incentives due to patent protection, which usually stimulate the aggressive marketing of new pharmaceuticals. These financial incentives were lacking in the case of micronutrients. However, these factors do not explain the anger and scorn illustrated in the quotations from medical textbooks given in their paper. Goodwin and Tangum rightly asked [13.3]:

“Where did the emotion come from?

Why did academic medicine deploy the strongly negative language of denunciation against proponents of vitamin supplements?”

13.1. Apple RD. *Vitamina: Vitamins in American Culture*; Rutgers University Press: Hoboken, NJ, USA, 1996.

Book reviews:

Gratzer W. Fruits and nuts. *Nature*. 1996;383:589-0.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/383589a0>

Whorton JC. Vitamins and science. *Pharmacy in History*. 1996;38:153-4.

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/41111767>

Baker SS. Vitamina: Vitamins in American culture. *N Engl J Med*. 1997;336:1112-3.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM199704103361525>

Opper FH. Vitamina: Vitamins in American Culture. *JAMA*. 1997;277(15):1247.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1997.03540390077041>

Carpenter KJ. Vitamina: Vitamins in American Culture. *Bulletin of the History of Medicine*. 1997;71(2):360-2.

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/44444861>

Vinikas V. Vitamina: Vitamins in American Culture. *Journal of Social History*. 1997;31(2):475-6.

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/3789967>

Kett JF. Vitamina: Vitamins in American Culture. *Journal of Interdisciplinary History*. 1997;28(2):315-6.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/206451>

Levenstein H. Vitamina: Vitamins in American Culture. *Journal of American History*. 1997;84(3):1094-5.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/2953175>

Kinsey JD. Vitamina: Vitamins in American Culture. *Journal of Consumer Affairs*. 1997;31:376-80.

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/23860485>

Jefferson JW. Vitamina: Vitamins in American Culture. *Wisconsin Mag History*. 1997;80:318-9.

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/4636711>

Bogin M. Vitamina: Vitamins in American Culture. *Technology and Culture*. 1998;39(4):804-6.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/1215875>

Horrocks SM. Vitamina: Vitamins in American Culture. *Isis*. 1998;89(1):168-9.

<https://doi.org/10.1086/383987>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/236720>

Kay G. Vitamina: Vitamins in American Culture. *Journal of the History of Medicine and Allied Sciences*. 1998;53(1):88-9.

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/24624260>

Vella F. Vitamina: Vitamins in American culture. *Biochemical Education*. 1998;26(1):91-2.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0307-4412\(98\)00064-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0307-4412(98)00064-8)

Holloway SWF. Vitamina: Vitamins in American culture. *Social History of Medicine*. 1998;11(1):163-4.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/shm/11.1.163>

Sherriff J. Vitamina: Vitamins in American Culture. *Journal of Biosocial Science*. 2001;33(4):627-8.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021932001246239>

13.2. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Bias against vitamin C in mainstream medicine: examples from trials of vitamin C for infections. *Life (Basel)*. 2022;12(1):62.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/life12010062>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8779885>

13.3. Goodwin JS, Tangum MR. Battling quackery: Attitudes about micronutrient supplements in American academic medicine. *Arch. Intern. Med.* 1998;158:2187-91.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/archinte.158.20.2187>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/13467491>

see also:

Goodwin JS, Goodwin JM. The tomato effect. Rejection of highly efficacious therapies. *JAMA*. 1984;251(18):2387-90.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.251.18.2387>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/16827181>